

On the Intersection of a Line and an Archimedean Spiral

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Abstract

The problem discussed in this project arose quite unexpectedly for the author in connection with another [project](#) in the field of physics - the problem of non-simultaneous gravitational interaction between two bodies. The existence of a finite possible speed for the propagation of information and interactions - the speed of light - necessitates calculating the effect of the time interval between the 'emission' of the gravitational signal - whether this 'gravitational signal' is interpreted as the curvature of space-time or otherwise - and its 'reception' by another body. (According to the simulation conducted in this project, the main effect consists of the rotation of the orbit of the bodies in the direction of motion along this orbit). Calculating this time delay ultimately boiled down to finding the intersection point between an Archimedean spiral and a linear function. The linear function represents the rectilinear and uniform motion of the receiving body, while the spiral represents the trajectory of the point from the expanding spherical wavefront, which will intersect in space with the rectilinear trajectory of the receiving body at a certain moment in time.

Finding this intersection point, however, turned out to be possible only through the use of a numerical method, as no analytical method exists. In the project itself, a numerical method was used, but the challenge of discovering an analytical method remained. This current project will present an attempt to formulate such an analytical method using elementary geometry of a right triangle and the central angle of a radius vector.

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1 General Strategy

The project sets two main objectives:

1. To develop an analytical method for calculating the intersection points between two mathematical objects - a straight line and an Archimedean spiral.
2. To express this method in mathematical form.

For the first objective, it will be necessary to parameterize the Archimedean spiral.

The second objective involves defining a special type of functions, which, for convenience, will be referred to as *reduction functions*.

1.1 Parameterization of an Archimedean spiral

The formula for the Archimedean spiral is:

$$r = a + b\theta, \tag{1.1.1}$$

where

- r is the radius of the spiral (the distance from the center of the spiral to the point).
- θ is the angle in polar coordinates (measured in radians).
- a is the initial radius (the distance from the center when $\theta = 0$).
- b determines the distance between the turns of the spiral (the rate of expansion).

If we want to express the Archimedean spiral component-wise in the Cartesian coordinate system, we will have the following two equations:

$$x_s = r\cos\theta, \tag{1.1.2}$$

$$y_s = r \sin \theta. \quad (1.1.3)$$

The equations for x_s and y_s of an Archimedean spiral in the Cartesian coordinate system are not functions because, due to the periodicity of the sine and cosine functions, there are multiple values for x_s and y_s for each value of the angle of rotation θ . To solve this problem, we will use standard parameterization for the two equations by introducing the parameter t .

The Archimedean spiral can be thought of as the trajectory of one point rotating around another point - the center. It represents the simplest case of a combination of the two types of motion: the rotation of a point around another point at a constant angular velocity, combined with a change in distance (radius) at a constant linear velocity. Therefore, it makes sense for the Archimedean spiral to be represented as a process over time, i.e., as a function of t . If we place the point around which the other point rotates at the center of the Cartesian coordinate system, then the distance between the two can be represented as a radius vector.

$$\vec{R}(t) = vt. \quad (1.1.4)$$

In this project, we will consider only non-negative values for time. The velocity v will also be taken as non-negative since the spiral is expanding from the center of the coordinate system.

Similarly to the increase of the radius vector, we will represent the angle of rotation as increasing linearly as a function of time.

$$\theta = \omega t. \quad (1.1.5)$$

where ω is the angular velocity, which can take positive and negative values corresponding to the direction of rotation, counterclockwise and clockwise, respectively.

When $\omega = 0$, there is no rotation, and therefore, there is no spiral.

Substituting the last two equations into 1.1.2 and 1.1.3 for x_s and y_s , we get:

$$x_s(t) = vt \cos(\omega t), \quad (1.1.6)$$

$$y_s(t) = vt \sin(\omega t), \quad (1.1.7)$$

where $r = \vec{R} = vt$.

These equations cannot be solved analytically because t is a multiplier both outside and inside the trigonometric functions, and it cannot be removed from them. Therefore, it is not possible to isolate the parameter t on one side of the equation.

In other words, we cannot analytically determine the value of t for given values of x_s , y_s , v and ω . In situations like this, numerical methods with approximations are usually employed. Here, we will also do this, with the difference that the first value of the algorithm

is not arbitrary, but derived analytically.

The last two formulas, in this form, have the limitation of defining only an Archimedean spiral with an initial angle equal to zero. In fact, a spiral can start unfolding from another initial angle. For example, 45 degrees. To correct this, we will introduce the initial angle θ_0 into the trigonometric functions. Thus, the equations take the form:

$$x_s(t) = v t \cos(\theta_0 + \omega t), \quad 0 \leq \theta_0 < 2\pi, \quad (1.1.8)$$

$$y_s(t) = v t \sin(\theta_0 + \omega t), \quad 0 \leq \theta_0 < 2\pi. \quad (1.1.9)$$

We introduce this restriction in the domain of θ_0 for simplicity and easier work with this parameter. We will also add another representation of it as a multiple of $\pi/2$. For this purpose, we introduce the parameter k , which, due to the restriction of θ_0 , will have values between 0 and 4.

$$\theta_0 = k \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad 0 \leq k < 4. \quad (1.1.10)$$

Then

$$x_s(t) = v t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), \quad (1.1.11)$$

$$y_s(t) = v t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t). \quad (1.1.12)$$

Expressing the initial angle as a multiple of $\pi/2$ has some significant advantages for reasons that will be clarified later in the exposition.

Formulas 1.1.11 and 1.1.12 provide a complete mathematical description of all possible Archimedean spirals. If we look at them from a slightly more general perspective, we can say that they represent a transformation of time into space coordinates. The algorithm that will be presented here is based on the inverse transformation - space coordinates to time. In this sense, it can be thought of as the inverse function of these formulas, although it is incomparably more complex.

1.2 Algebraic checks and reduction functions

The second main objective of this project — expressing the method for finding the intersection points between a straight line and an Archimedean spiral purely mathematically — necessitates the definition of functions whose role is to reduce a real number (the input parameter of the function) to several possible values, most often two or three, based on some properties of the number. These functions serve the same purpose as *if-else* checks in programming languages. In essence, they are their mathematical equivalent.

The problem of finding intersection points is deeply connected to performing numerous conditional checks and making decisions about how to compute these points based on the configuration of the spiral and line parameters. For instance, whether the spiral rotates clockwise or counterclockwise — i.e., the sign of the angular velocity ω ; in which quadrant the initial angle θ_0 is located — i.e., the parameter k ; the position of the line relative to the coordinate axes, and so on. These checks are straightforward to perform

in a programming language, but the goal here is to derive a mathematical equation.

In mathematics, reduction functions are already defined. One example of such a function is the *indicator* function.

$$f(x) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } x \in A, \\ 0, & \text{if } x \notin A, \end{cases} \quad (1.2.1)$$

where A is some set, but it is essentially the same as if-else statements and cannot be directly included in a mathematical expression.

Another reduction function that can be directly applied in a mathematical expression is the *sigmoid* function.

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{1 + e^{-x}}, \quad (1.2.2)$$

but it has the following two disadvantages:

1. It does not provide an exact value.
2. It requires intensive computations for large values of x .

For the purposes of this project, such computations are not necessary.

1.3 Basic reduction functions

We will define several basic reduction functions that will serve as the foundation for algebraic condition checks. They consist of operations with standard mathematical operations - addition, subtraction, multiplication, exponentiation, etc. - on real variables. We will also define a special notation for them. This is necessary for better readability and to avoid overloading the mathematical expression of the final equation for the intersection points, which is very long and practically unreadable. The notation is as follows:

$$Name_{(inputs)}^{[outputs]} = expression. \quad (1.3.1)$$

On the left-hand side of the equation, we place the name of the function. It can be a single letter, an abbreviation, a word, or an expression. If it is a single letter, it should be uppercase. If it is an abbreviation, the letters should also be uppercase. If it is a word, the first letter should be uppercase and the rest lowercase. If it is an expression, the words are written together, with each word starting with an uppercase letter. The reasons for adopting this notation are as follows:

1. Uppercase letters - if the function is named with a single letter, we use an uppercase letter to avoid confusion with a regular variable, constant, or parameter. We will use single letters for the basic reduction functions, as they will be used most frequently.
2. When the name is a full word or an expression, we use uppercase initial letters for better readability. When the reduction function is very specific, we follow the programming practice of giving it a short, descriptive name.

After the function's name, we place the arguments in the lower-right index in round brackets, separated by commas. The reason we do not put the arguments in parentheses immediately after the function's name is to avoid confusion with a standard function.

In the upper-right index, we use square brackets to record the outputs of the function.

The first basic function we will define is a function that checks whether its argument is a non-integer or not. We will call it B .

$$B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lceil x \rceil - \lfloor x \rfloor, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (1.3.2)$$

$$B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (1.3.3)$$

$$B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x \notin \mathbb{Z}. \quad (1.3.4)$$

Here we should note that the mathematical operations in a reduction function are determined by the way the question the function "checks" is posed. A function $B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ defined this way, returns 1 - i.e., the mathematical equivalent of the logical statement *True*, or in response to the question: 'Is the argument x a non-integer?' the function $B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ "answers" affirmatively by returning 1 and negatively by returning 0.

If we pose the question the other way around: 'Is the argument x an integer?' then we need to define the mathematical operations in the function differently.

$$\overline{B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 1 - (\lceil x \rceil - \lfloor x \rfloor), \quad (1.3.5)$$

$$\overline{B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 1, \quad x \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (1.3.6)$$

$$\overline{B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 0, \quad x \notin \mathbb{Z}. \quad (1.3.7)$$

Everything depends on the need and context for which we formulate each specific reduction function. This logical inversion of the result will be very useful for the intersection equation, where, in some places, it will be necessary for certain parts of it to "activate" simultaneously with the "deactivation" of others. In such cases, we will refer to the combination of two opposite reduction functions as *switches*.

The function $B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ will have only one application in the formula, and that is in the analytical derivation of the initial value of t , which is provided to the algorithm. Apart from this in the appendix following the main exposition we will see how this function can be used to find the factorials and sums of prime and composite numbers up to a given number n and the count of prime and composite numbers up to n .

The next basic reduction function we will define aims to determine whether its argument is different from zero. We will call it $X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$.

$$X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = x^{0^{|x|}}, \quad (1.3.8)$$

$$X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (1.3.9)$$

$$X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.10)$$

We place the absolute value of the argument x to the power of zero, as zero cannot be raised to a negative power.

The definition of this function concerns a very controversial question in mathematics - what is the value of 0^0 . There are three views on this value. One is that $0^0 = 1$, the second - $0^0 = 0$, and the third - $0^0 = \text{undefined}$. There are arguments for and against each of these views. Some programming languages, such as *Python* and *JavaScript*, adopt the first view for purely practical reasons, as it saves performing a check.

To define the function $X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$, we need to adopt the convention $0^0 = 1$. Without this assumption it would not be possible to perform algebraic conditional checks through mathematical operations in the equation.

In several parts of the equation, we will need to use the reduction function $X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ as a *switch*. For this purpose, we define its "opposite function" - $\overline{X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}}$.

$$\overline{X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 1 - X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}, \quad (1.3.11)$$

$$\overline{X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 1 - x^{0^{|x|}}, \quad (1.3.12)$$

$$\overline{X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 0, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (1.3.13)$$

$$\overline{X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 1, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.14)$$

The following example demonstrates how a *switch* can be used. Let us consider a mathematical expression A . We want it to compute the sum of two parameters a and b when $x \neq 0$, and the difference between a and b when $x = 0$.

$$A = X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}(a + b) + \overline{X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}}(a - b), \quad (1.3.15)$$

$$A = 1(a + b) + 0(a - b) = a + b, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (1.3.16)$$

$$A = 0(a + b) + 1(a - b) = a - b, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.17)$$

As can be seen, this *switch* is the algebraic equivalent of the *if-else* conditional statement in programming. Furthermore, it can reasonably be regarded as the mathematical analog of a *transistor* component in electronics, as it literally activates and deactivates — allowing or blocking "current" to - specific components of the expression A .

If we remove the notation for the reduction functions and leave only the algebraic operations, then A will look like this:

$$A = x^{0^{|x|}}(a + b) + (1 - x^{0^{|x|}})(a - b), \quad (1.3.18)$$

For short expressions like this, the pure algebraic form of the *switch* is still understandable. However, in the presentation below, we will see that the notation of reduction functions is preferable.

We will note that the reduction function $X_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ can take as an argument not only a single value but also a sum or product of values, entire functions, etc.

The next basic reduction function we will define is a function that determines the sign of its argument. It will return 1 when the argument is positive and -1 when it is negative. We will call it the *sign function* and denote it as $S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee\text{undefined}\vee 1]}$.

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee\text{undefined}\vee 1]} = \frac{x}{|x|}, \quad (1.3.19)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee\text{undefined}\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > 0, \quad (1.3.20)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee\text{undefined}\vee 1]} = -1, \quad x < 0, \quad (1.3.21)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee\text{undefined}\vee 1]} = \text{undefined}, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.22)$$

Defined in this way, this function has the drawback of being undefined at $x = 0$. If executed by a program, it will throw a *division by zero error*. This necessitates introducing a conditional check for $x = 0$ in the program. To resolve this issue, we will need to construct the function $S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee\text{undefined}\vee 1]}$ in such a way that it algebraically avoids division by zero. For this purpose, we will define another function whose role is to eliminate zero. We will call this function the *eliminative function* and denote it by $E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]}$.

$$E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]} = x^{1-0^{|x|}}, \quad (1.3.23)$$

$$E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]} = x, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (1.3.24)$$

$$E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]} = 1, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.25)$$

As can be seen, this function replaces the value of the argument x with 1 if $x = 0$. For all other values of the argument, the function returns the argument itself. Using this, we can replace the denominator in $S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee\text{undefined}\vee 1]}$ with the *eliminative function* and algebraically resolve the problem of division by zero.

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{x}{|E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (1.3.26)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{0}{|1|} = 0. \quad (1.3.27)$$

The eliminative function allows the program to continue running without the need for a conditional check. This is how the complete definition of the *sign function* $S_{(x)}^{[-1,0,1]}$ looks.

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{x}{|E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (1.3.28)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > 0, \quad (1.3.29)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = -1, \quad x < 0, \quad (1.3.30)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.31)$$

Now we need to focus more on the eliminative function $E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]}$. We will define an eliminative function of a sum and product, as well as the sum and product of eliminative functions. We will remove the square brackets with the function outputs for easier readability.

Let $a, b \in \mathbb{R}$.

Eliminative function of a sum:

$$E_{(a+b)} = a + b, \quad a \neq 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.32)$$

$$E_{(a+b)} = b, \quad a = 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.33)$$

$$E_{(a+b)} = 1, \quad a = 0, \quad b = 0. \quad (1.3.34)$$

Sum of eliminative functions:

$$E_{(a)} + E_{(b)} = a + b, \quad a \neq 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.35)$$

$$E_{(a)} + E_{(b)} = 1 + b, \quad a = 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.36)$$

$$E_{(a)} + E_{(b)} = 2, \quad a = 0, \quad b = 0. \quad (1.3.37)$$

We can see that:

$$E_{(a+b)} \neq E_{(a)} + E_{(b)}, \quad a = 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.38)$$

$$E_{(a+b)} \neq E_{(a)} + E_{(b)}, \quad a = 0, \quad b = 0. \quad (1.3.39)$$

Eliminative function of a product:

$$E_{(ab)} = ab, \quad a \neq 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.40)$$

$$E_{(ab)} = 1, \quad a = 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.41)$$

$$E_{(ab)} = 1, \quad a = 0, \quad b = 0. \quad (1.3.42)$$

Product of eliminative functions:

$$E_{(a)}E_{(b)} = ab, \quad a \neq 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.43)$$

$$E_{(a)}E_{(b)} = b, \quad a = 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.44)$$

$$E_{(a)}E_{(b)} = 1, \quad a = 0, \quad b = 0. \quad (1.3.45)$$

We can see that:

$$E_{(ab)} \neq E_{(a)}E_{(b)}, \quad a = 0, \quad b \neq 0, \quad (1.3.46)$$

$$E_{(a+b)} = E_{(ab)}, \quad a = 0, \quad b = 0, \quad (1.3.47)$$

$$E_{(a+b)} = E_{(a)}E_{(b)}, \quad a = 0, \quad b \neq 0. \quad (1.3.48)$$

A more thorough analysis of the possibilities provided by the eliminative function will be presented in the Appendix.

The last two basic reduction functions we will define will perform an algebraic check to determine whether a given value is greater than or less than another given value. We will call them $Greater_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ and $Less_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ where x is the value we are checking, while l is the boundary against which we are checking x .

$$Greater_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{x-l}{|E_{(x-l)}^{[1\vee x-l]}|}}{2} \rfloor, \quad (1.3.49)$$

$$Greater_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > l, \quad (1.3.50)$$

$$Greater_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x \leq l, \quad (1.3.51)$$

$$Less_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 - \frac{x-l}{|E_{(x-l)}^{[1\vee x-l]}|}}{2} \rfloor, \quad (1.3.52)$$

$$Less_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x < l, \quad (1.3.53)$$

$$Less_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x \geq l. \quad (1.3.54)$$

With the help of these two basic reduction functions, we can construct more complex algebraic checks, such as verifying whether a given variable lies within a certain interval. Let us consider x , l_{left} and l_{right} . We can algebraically ask whether $x \in (l_{left}, l_{right})$.

$$A = Greater_{(x,l_{left})}^{[0\vee 1]} Less_{(x,l_{right})}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{x-l_{left}}{|E_{(x-l_{left})}^{[1\vee x-l_{left}]}}|}}{2} \rfloor \lfloor \frac{1 - \frac{x-l_{right}}{|E_{(x-l_{right})}^{[1\vee x-l_{right}]}}|}}{2} \rfloor. \quad (1.3.55)$$

From a logical perspective, we perform a conjunction between the two statements, while from an algebraic perspective, we take the product of the two functions. If necessary, the logic can easily be inverted by subtracting the respective function from 1.

1.4 Overview of the General Strategy

Building upon the parameterization of the spiral and the reduction functions, we can broadly outline the workings of the algorithm for finding the intersection points between a straight line and a spiral.

1. The parameterization of the Archimedean spiral by components allows the spiral curve to be represented as a function - each point on the curve corresponds to exactly one parameter value t_n , or each point on the curve is localized at exactly one moment t_n .
2. Consequently, the task consists of finding the moments t_n at which the spiral curve intersects the straight line.
3. These moments are determined through a series of precisely calculated rotations of the spiral's radius vector. This series of rotations asymptotically approximates the radius vector toward the point where the spiral curve intersects the straight line.
4. The algorithm is iterative - each subsequent iteration t_n uses the moment t_{n-1} calculated in the previous iteration as its input.
5. The initial moments t_n are analytically derived based on elementary geometric relationships between the current radius vector and the parameters of the line. In other words, this involves a transformation from *space* to *time*.
6. There are two ways to perform such a transformation: one uses angles to calculate time intervals, while the other uses lengths to calculate exact moments.
7. These two types of transformations are implemented in two separate algorithms. One is called the *Angle-Based Algorithm (AB-Alg)*, which is the primary algorithm for finding the intersection points. The other is called the *Length-Based Algorithm (LB-Alg)*, which is applied in special cases where the *AB-Alg* fails.
8. The starting time values t_n for both algorithms are analytically derived. They are not arbitrary. Therefore, the method is a hybrid numerical-analytical method, rather than a purely numerical one.
9. For its proper functioning, the numerical-analytical method relies on algebraic checks. These checks play a critical role both outside and within the algorithms. Outside, they "decide" which of the two algorithms to activate based on the current configuration of parameters. Within the algorithms, algebraic checks are used to determine parameter signs, rotation direction, activation or deactivation of certain values, and more.

In conclusion, the method consists of two iterative algorithms and numerous algebraic checks.

We will begin the explanation of the method with the main algorithm.

2 Numerical-analytical method for finding intersection points between an Archimedean spiral and a straight line

Let's start with a graphical representation of the problem of intersection points.

Figure 1

(Note: All images were generated using a game simulation for drawing lines and spirals, which is available for download [here](#). Following the general strategy, in the code the equation for the intersection points is written entirely in mathematical form, without any conditional checks written in a programming language.)

We position the spiral with arbitrary parameters v , ω and k at the center of the coordinate system. We need to find all the points where the spiral curve intersects the straight line with arbitrary parameters a and b and equation

$$y = ax + b, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.0.1)$$

where a is the slope of the line relative to the positive x -axis, and b is the intersection point of the line with the y -axis.

All we have as information for the two objects are the three parameters of the spiral and the two parameters of the line.

2.1 Angle-Based Algorithm

We will start deriving the formula for the main algorithm by taking the special case of a vertical line - that is, a line parallel to the y -axis - positioned at a specific point on the x -axis, denoted by x_l . This line has an infinite slope a and no intersection b with the y -axis. Therefore, it cannot be represented by the equation 2.0.1 Its equation is thus:

$$x_l = c, \quad c \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (2.1.1)$$

where c is the fixed value of the x -coordinate for every point on the line. *Figure 2* illustrates a vertical line positioned at the point $x_l = 1$. This line intersects the spiral curve at infinitely many points. The task of finding the intersection points between this vertical line and the spiral is equivalent to determining the moments t_n , when the x -component of the parametric curve takes the values $x_s = x_l$ (in this case $x_l = 1$).

Figure 2

As already demonstrated, this problem has no analytical solution. More precisely, there is no analytical solution when $x_l \neq 0$. However, an analytical solution exists when $x_l = 0$, i.e., when the line coincides with the y -axis. The y -axis, after all, is also a straight line; it is simply positioned at the center of the coordinate system along the x -axis. An analytical solution for $x_l = 0$ exists because the exact moments t_n , when the spiral intersects the y -axis, can be calculated through angle transformation. Since the spiral starts to unfold from the center of the coordinate system, the rotation of its radius vector describes a central angle. Therefore, the angle at which the radius vector must rotate to intersect the y -axis can be computed analytically.

In *Figure 2*, the spiral begins to unfold counterclockwise with an initial angle of 0 degrees or $k = 0$. On the left side of the image, these correspond to w (in the images, we will use w instead of ω due to technical reasons), k and **Start angle**. The radius vector, therefore, must be rotated by 90 degrees to intersect the y -axis. Given this angle, its transformation over time is governed by the angular velocity ω from the formula 1.1.5. Expressing t we have:

$$t = \frac{\theta}{\omega}. \quad (2.1.2)$$

In Figure 3, we have $\omega = 1$, $k = 0$, Start angle $\theta_0 = 0$ degrees, $\Delta\theta = 90$ degrees ($\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians).

Figure 3

All other intersection points with the y -axis are located at angles that are multiples of 180 degrees after the first intersection point and can be easily computed. These points will serve as the initial values entered into the iterative *Angle-Based Algorithm*. In this sense, the method is numerically-analytical.

Before we begin with the algorithm itself, the first task is to find the first intersection point of the spiral with the y -axis.

2.2 Analytical derivation of input values

Finding the first intersection point of the spiral curve with the y -axis means calculating two values:

1. The magnitude of the rotation angle of the radius vector.
2. Its direction.

The two values depend respectively on the two parameters: the initial angle of the spiral's unfolding θ_0 as a function of the parameter k , and the sign of the angular velocity ω

Figure 4

Figure 5

The two images above show spirals with the same initial angle $\theta_0 = 315$ degrees ($k = 3.5$), but with different signs of angular velocity ω . In *Figure 4*, the spiral's radius vector needs to rotate 135 degrees anticlockwise, while in *Figure 5*, it needs to rotate 45 degrees clockwise.

The algorithm for finding the first intersection point of the spiral curve with the ordinate axis consists of three parts:

1. Calculating the magnitude of the angle of rotation of the radius vector to the nearest coordinate axis in the direction of the spiral's unwinding. The nearest coordinate axis can be either the ordinate or the abscissa.
2. If the nearest coordinate axis is the abscissa, then 90 degrees ($\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians) must be added to the calculated angle of rotation to reach the next ordinate axis. This is the reason we chose to express the initial angle of the spiral as a multiple of $\frac{\pi}{2}$.
3. The resulting angle must be transformed into a time interval Δt . Since the initial value of t is zero, the given interval can be considered as a moment in time relative to $t = 0$.

To distinguish the successive moments at which the spiral intersects the ordinate axis, we will place a right-hand subscript n after t . Thus, the moment of the first intersection with the ordinate axis will be denoted as t_1 , the moment of the second intersection as t_2 , and so on. Therefore, for the first intersection point, we have:

$$t_1 = \frac{\Delta\theta}{|\omega|}. \quad (2.2.1)$$

Note: For greater clarity in the formulas, we will adopt the strategy of calculating the absolute values of angles, lengths, etc., and performing operations with these values through algebraic checks. Therefore, in the above formula, we take the absolute value of ω along with the fact that we have defined the parameter t as a non-negative quantity.

Furthermore, we will pass ω as an argument to the *eliminative function* to avoid program interruption with a *division by zero error* when the sign of ω changes.

$$t_1 = \frac{\Delta\theta}{|E_{(\omega)}^{[1 \vee \omega]}|}, \quad (2.2.2)$$

$$t_1 = \frac{\Delta\theta}{1} = \Delta\theta, \quad \omega = 0. \quad (2.2.3)$$

When $\omega = 0$ the *eliminative function* returns one, leading to $t_1 = \Delta\theta$. But this is not correct. *Figures 6 and 7* show that the program does not terminate at $\omega = 0$, but instead of plotting a spiral curve, it draws a straight line. This makes sense - when the angular velocity equals zero, there is no rotation, and thus no spiral. Consequently, there can be no intersection of the spiral with the ordinate axis. However, this does not mean that the radius vector does not grow. This is a consequence of the spiral's parameterization. Let us revisit the formulas 1.1.11 and 1.1.12.

$$x_s(t) = v t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), \quad (1.1.11)$$

$$y_s(t) = v t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t). \quad (1.1.12)$$

At $\omega = 0$ we have

$$x_s(t) = v t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2}), \quad (2.2.4)$$

$$y_s(t) = v t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2}). \quad (2.2.5)$$

The radius vector exists but does not rotate. That's why *Spiral angle* = 0 degrees.

Figure 6

Figure 7

Paradoxically, the eliminative function allows for the calculation of values that do not actually exist. This issue will be addressed in more detail in the Appendix.

The first task is to express $\Delta\theta$ from formula 2.2.2 as a function of k and the sign of ω . Following step 2 of the algorithm for finding the first intersection point, we need to determine the next coordinate axis relative to the initial angle of the spiral's unwinding θ_0 and the direction of the angular velocity ω .

The initial angle as a function of k is expressed using the following formula:

$$\theta_0(k) = k \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (2.2.6)$$

As a starting point, we will identify the next coordinate axis solely for positive angular velocity values. This is illustrated graphically in *Figures 8 and 9*. The black radius vector represents the initial angle $\theta_0(k)$, while the red one indicates the next coordinate axis in the anticlockwise direction.

Figure 8

Figure 9

We aim to determine how much the black radius vector should rotate in the counterclockwise direction. This angle will be denoted as $\Delta\theta(k)^+$, with the plus sign in the upper right index indicating that the angular velocity is currently positive. For $\Delta\theta(k)^+$, we have the following formula:

$$\Delta\theta(k)^+ = \lfloor k + 1 \rfloor \frac{\pi}{2} - \theta_0(k). \quad (2.2.7)$$

Replacing $\theta_0(k)$ from 2.2.6

$$\Delta\theta(k)^+ = \lfloor k + 1 \rfloor \frac{\pi}{2} - k \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (2.2.8)$$

$$\Delta\theta(k)^+ = (\lfloor k + 1 \rfloor - k) \frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (2.2.9)$$

Our goal, however, is to determine the next ordinate axis. As shown in *Figure 8*, an additional angle of $\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians needs to be added to reach the next ordinate axis. In contrast, in *Figure 9*, no additional angle is required. Therefore, we will rely on an algebraic check.

As seen in both figures, the criterion is whether the integer part of the parameter k is even or odd. This check will be performed using the reduction function $B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]}$. Let us recall its definition:

$$B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lceil x \rceil - \lfloor x \rfloor, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (1.3.2)$$

$$B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (1.3.3)$$

$$B_{(x)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x \notin \mathbb{Z}. \quad (1.3.4)$$

The purpose of this function is to check whether its argument is a fraction. This can easily be adapted into a check for whether the integer part of the argument is even or odd by providing the following expression as an argument:

$$x = \frac{\lfloor k \rfloor}{2}. \quad (2.2.10)$$

Then

$$B_{\left(\frac{\lfloor k \rfloor}{2}\right)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad \{k \in \mathbb{Z} \mid k = 2n, n \in \mathbb{Z}\} \quad (2.2.11)$$

$$B_{\left(\frac{\lfloor k \rfloor}{2}\right)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad \{k \in \mathbb{Z} \mid k = 2n + 1, n \in \mathbb{Z}\}. \quad (2.2.12)$$

We add 1.3.2 to 2.2.9.

$$\Delta\theta(k)^+ = ([k + 1] - k + B_{(\frac{\lfloor k \rfloor}{2})}^{[0\vee 1]})\frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (2.2.13)$$

The idea here is that the reduction function with this argument "commands" the equation.

If:

- The integer part of k is odd, then the next coordinate axis in the counterclockwise direction is the x -axis. In this case, add 1 to k (i.e., $\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians).

If:

- The integer part is even and the next axis is the y -axis - do not add $\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians (algebraically - add 0).

Figure 10 shows the same initial angle and direction of rotation as Figure 8 , but with the corrected next ordinate axis obtained through the formula above.

Figure 10

Similarly, we will derive an equation for the direction of rotation clockwise - $\omega < 0$.

$$\Delta\theta(k)^- = (k - [k] + B_{(\frac{\lfloor k+1 \rfloor}{2})}^{[0\vee 1]})\frac{\pi}{2}. \quad (2.2.14)$$

Figure 11

Figure 12

Now, we will combine the two equations to derive a general solution to the problem. For this purpose, we will use two other reduction functions to construct a *switch*. These are the functions $Greather_{(x)}^{[0V1]}$ and $Less_{(x)}^{[0V1]}$, which will take the angular velocity as their argument.

$$Greather_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}}{2} \rfloor, \quad (2.2.15)$$

$$Greather_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} = 1, \quad \omega > 0, \quad (2.2.16)$$

$$Greather_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} = 0, \quad \omega \leq 0, \quad (2.2.17)$$

$$Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 - \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}}{2} \rfloor \quad (2.2.18)$$

$$Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} = 1, \quad \omega < 0, \quad (2.2.19)$$

$$Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} = 0, \quad \omega \geq 0. \quad (2.2.20)$$

Schematically, the general solution appears as follows:

$$\Delta\theta(\omega, k) = \left(Greather_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- \right) \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad (2.2.21)$$

$$\Delta\theta(\omega, k) = (1\Delta\theta(k)^+ + 0\Delta\theta(k)^-) \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad \omega > 0, \quad (2.2.22)$$

$$\Delta\theta(\omega, k) = (0\Delta\theta(k)^+ + 1\Delta\theta(k)^-) \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad \omega < 0, \quad (2.2.23)$$

$$\Delta\theta(\omega, k) = (0\Delta\theta(k)^+ + 0\Delta\theta(k)^-) \frac{\pi}{2}, \quad \omega = 0. \quad (2.2.24)$$

The 'instruction' provided by the *switch* is as follows:

If $\omega > 0$:

- Reset formula for $\Delta\theta(k)^-$ and calculate the angle to the next ordinate axis using formula for $\Delta\theta(k)^+$.

If $\omega < 0$:

- Reset formula for $\Delta\theta(k)^+$ and calculate the angle to the next ordinate axis using formula for $\Delta\theta(k)^-$.

If $\omega = 0$:

- Reset both formulas.

Figure 13 illustrates what happens when $\omega = 0$.

Figure 13

As previously mentioned, in the case of $\omega = 0$, the spiral does not exist, and therefore, there is no intersection of the radius vector with the coordinate axes. The two vectors coincide.

Let us now present the general solution for $\Delta\theta(w, k)$ in pure algebraic form.

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta\theta(w, k) = & \left(\left[\frac{1 + \frac{\omega}{\omega_0^{|\omega|}}}{2} \right] \left(\lfloor k+1 \rfloor - k + \left\lceil \frac{\lfloor k+1 \rfloor}{2} \right\rceil - \left\lfloor \frac{\lfloor k+1 \rfloor}{2} \right\rfloor \right) \right. \\ & \left. + \left[\frac{1 - \frac{\omega}{\omega_0^{|\omega|}}}{2} \right] \left(k - \lfloor k \rfloor + \left\lceil \frac{\lfloor k+1 \rfloor}{2} \right\rceil - \left\lfloor \frac{\lfloor k+1 \rfloor}{2} \right\rfloor \right) \right) \frac{\pi}{2}. \end{aligned} \quad (2.2.25)$$

Here, we replaced all the reduction functions with their algebraic definitions. The equation has now become difficult to read, and this is only the input value for the *Angle-Based Algorithm*. Therefore, in the following exposition, we will adhere to the strategy of writing the functions by their names in the equation, rather than their algebraic forms.

Let us now substitute the derived formula for $\Delta\theta(w, k)$ into 2.2.2 to transform the angular interval into time.

$$t_1 = \frac{\Delta\theta}{|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}, \quad (2.2.2)$$

$$t_1 = \frac{\pi \left(Greater_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}. \quad (2.2.26)$$

As noted above, the eliminative function does not allow 0 in the denominator. This means that the function remains defined even when $\omega = 0$. On the other hand, in this case, the spiral curve does not exist, and therefore the moment t , when the spiral intersects the ordinate axis, also does not exist. Nevertheless, the formula returns a value. In this specific case, it is $t_1 = 0$, and this arises from the way we derived $\Delta\theta(w, k)$.

That is, we can observe that the eliminative function allows the domain of definition of a given function to be extended for the value of the argument where it is undefined. The question is, what should the value of the function be at this argument value? The answer is that this value can be introduced arbitrarily. More on this in the Appendix.

Finally, after analytically deriving the initial value t_1 for the angular algorithm, we can determine all subsequent moments t_n at which the spiral curve intersects the ordinate axis. Once again, we will transform angles into time intervals. All angles at which the spiral intersects the ordinate axis are multiples of 180 degrees relative to the first angle.

$$t_n = \frac{\pi \left(Greater_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- \right) + (n-1)\pi}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}, \quad (2.2.27)$$

$$t_n = \frac{\pi \left(Greater_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- + (n-1) \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}. \quad (2.2.28)$$

Figure 14 illustrates the arrangement of the intersection points between the spiral curve and the ordinate axis.

Figure 14

The additional term $(n-1)$, which we introduced into the formula, once again demonstrates that the eliminative function allows a given function to return values that do not exist. For $\omega = 0$, we have:

- $t_1 = 0$
- $t_2 = \frac{\pi}{2}$
- $t_3 = \pi$
- $t_4 = \frac{3\pi}{2}$

- $t_5 = 2\pi$
- and so on...

Formula 2.2.28 is the final formula used to analytically derive the initial time values t_n , which will be input into the iterative *Angle-Based Algorithm*.

3 Description and General Strategy of the Angle-Based Algorithm

The goal of the *Angle-Based Algorithm* is to execute a series of rotations of the spiral's radius vector toward its intersection with the vertical line. The rotations are determined by an angular difference $\Delta\phi$, which is transformed into time t . Unlike the formula for determining the initial values, which transforms space into time only once, the algorithm involves two transformations in the following sequence:

$$Time - > Space - > Time$$

In each iteration, the algorithm performs this double transformation. The steps are as follows:

1. Takes its initial input value t_0 from formula 2.2.28 or t_{n-1} from previous iteration.
2. Converts this value into the coordinates of the spiral's radius vector using the formulas:

$$x_s(t_{n-1}) = vt_{n-1}\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{n-1}), \quad (3.0.1)$$

$$y_s(t_{n-1}) = vt_{n-1}\sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{n-1}). \quad (3.0.2)$$

3. Determines the relationship of these coordinates to the point x_l where the vertical line is positioned, i.e.:
 - Computes the absolute value (magnitude) of the angular difference $\Delta\phi$ between the tip of the radius vector and its projection on the vertical line.
 - 'Decides' the direction in which to rotate the radius vector through algebraic checks.
4. Transforms the obtained angular difference into time and adds (or subtracts) it from the input time value t_{n-1} .
5. Returns the new value t_n , which is then used as the input for the next iteration.

Since the algorithm is iterative and returns multiple values, it can also be viewed as a numerical sequence, just like the formula for initial values. That is, it constructs a numerical sequence t_m using a member of another numerical sequence t_n as its starting value. From this perspective, the numerical-analytical method for finding the intersection points between a line and a spiral can be regarded as a formula for the general term of a two-dimensional numerical sequence.

We adopt the following notation for the general term:

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} = Expression, \quad (3.0.3)$$

where n is the n -th moment in time when the spiral intersects the ordinate axis, and m is the m -th approximation of the spiral's radius vector towards the vertical line.

We separate n and m with semicolon in the index and represent them as an ordered pair to avoid confusion between them. For example, if we simply used t_{123} , it would be unclear whether this refers to the 23-rd approximation to the line from the first intersection point with the ordinate or the 3-rd approximation from the 12-th intersection point.

The algorithm itself, for simplicity, will be denoted by the abbreviation *AB-Alg*. It is a function of five parameters - $t_{[n;m-1]}$, v , ω , k and x_l . Then, formula 3.0.3 takes the following form:

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} = AB-Alg(t_{[n;m-1]}, v, \omega, k, x_l), \quad t_{[n;0]} = t_n, \quad v, \omega, k, x_l = const. \quad (3.0.4)$$

With $t_{[n;0]} = t_n$ we denote the zero-th approximation, which is the n -th input value from the numerical sequence $\{t_n\}$.

The four constants are the three parameters of the spiral: the rate of increase of the radius vector v , the angular velocity ω , and the coefficient of the initial angle k ; and the position x_l of the vertical line on the abscissa axis.

Following the description of the algorithm above, its algebraic form is as follows:

$$AB-Alg(t_{[n;m]}) = t_{[n;m-1]} + \Delta t(t_{[n;m-1]}, v, \omega, k, x_l). \quad (3.0.5)$$

Then, for the two-dimensional numerical sequence, we have:

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} = t_{[n;m-1]} + \Delta t(t_{[n;m-1]}, v, \omega, k, x_l). \quad (3.0.6)$$

The task, therefore, is to calculate $\Delta t(t_{[n;m-1]}, v, \omega, k, x_l)$, which for simplicity will be denoted as Δt_m from now on.

3.1 Derivation of the Angle-Based Algorithm

Let us consider an *Archimedean spiral* with a radial growth rate $v = 3$, an angular velocity $\omega = 2$, an initial angle coefficient $k = 3$ (start angle of 270 degrees), and a vertical line positioned at point $x_l = 2$.

Figure 15 illustrates this configuration.

Figure 15

Step 1

For this configuration of the spiral's parameters, formula 2.2.28 calculates the following values:

1. The angle of rotation $\Delta\theta$ of the spiral's radius vector (the black radius vector lying on the positive side of the ordinate axis) to the next ordinate axis in the direction of the spiral's rotation ($\omega > 0$) is equal to π (180 degrees).
2. This angle of rotation corresponds to the moment $t_1 = 1.57079\dots$

This is the moment of the first intersection $n = 1$ of the ordinate axis by the spiral's radius vector. The input value of the algorithm is $nth_t 1 = 1.57079\dots$ and accordingly, this is the zeroth approximation $mth_t 0$ to the vertical line.

Step 2

The obtained initial time value t_1 must be converted into the coordinates of the corresponding radius vector using formulas 3.0.1 and 3.0.2. In this case, the specific coordinate values are $x_s(t_1) = 0$ and $y_s(t_1) = 4.71238\dots$ (*Spiral x* and *Spiral y* on the image). As seen, the obtained radius vector of the spiral at moment t_1 lies on the next ordinate axis relative to its initial angle.

Step 3

To calculate the first approximation $m = 1$ of the radius vector of the spiral to the line, we need to construct a triangle between it, the center of the coordinate system, and the line. *Figure 16* shows the already calculated first approximation, where the black radius vector is the result of the calculation, and the green one is the initial radius vector, obtained as a function of the input value t_1 .

Figure 16

The image shows a right triangle with sides a , b and c (a - hypotenuse, b and c - legs) and an angle $\Delta\phi$ opposite the side c (we define the triangle by its sides, as we are interested in the magnitudes of the sides rather than the positions of its vertices). Our goal is to determine the magnitude of the angle $\Delta\phi_m$. We add the index m to indicate that this is the angle of the m -th iteration.

We construct the triangle based on the radius vector from the previous iteration, taking its y -coordinate and finding the distance between it and its projection onto the straight line positioned at point x_l (blue point on the image). This distance forms the side c . This point is then connected to the origin of the coordinate system, forming the side a , which serves as the hypotenuse of this right triangle. Then, we can easily find the angle $\Delta\phi_m$ using the cosine rule, as we know the lengths of all three sides.

The cosine rule for the leg c is:

$$c^2 = a^2 + b^2 - 2ab\cos\Delta\phi. \quad (3.1.1)$$

Solving for the angle $\Delta\phi$, we have:

$$\Delta\phi_m = \arccos\frac{a^2 + b^2 - c^2}{2ab}. \quad (3.1.2)$$

As seen from the image, the angle $\Delta\phi_m$ is a central angle, and therefore there exists a radius vector of the spiral whose angle is equal to $\frac{\pi}{2} - \Delta\phi_m$. This vector lies on the hypotenuse a of the right triangle (the black radius vector). However, there are infinitely many radius vectors of the spiral with this angle.

Important note: To isolate the radius vector of interest, we use the cosine rule, not the tangent of the hypotenuse, because the tangent is undefined when the angle is 90 degrees. This occurs when the line coincides with the ordinate axis $x_l = 0$. In this case, however, the intersection points of the spiral and the line are well-defined, and these are the intersection points obtained through the initial values algorithm.

The leg b represents the length of the radius vector from the previous iteration (the green radius vector, which lies on the positive part of the ordinate axis):

$$b = \sqrt{x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2}. \quad (3.1.3)$$

The leg c is the distance between the point x_l , where the line is positioned, and the x -coordinate of the radius vector from the previous iteration:

$$c = |x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|. \quad (3.1.4)$$

Here, we take the difference of the absolute values of the points.

The side a is the hypotenuse of the triangle formed between the projection of the y -coordinate of the radius vector from the previous iteration onto the vertical line and the origin of the coordinate system. Its length is:

$$a = \sqrt{y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + x_l^2}. \quad (3.1.5)$$

Substituting a , b and c in 3.1.2 for $\Delta\phi_m$ we obtain:

$$\Delta\phi_m = \arccos \frac{y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + x_l^2 + x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 - (|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)^2}{2\sqrt{(y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + x_l^2)(x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2)}}. \quad (3.1.6)$$

$$\Delta\phi_m = \arccos \frac{y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + |x_l x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|}{\sqrt{(y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + x_l^2)(x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2)}}. \quad (3.1.7)$$

In the denominator, we have a product where one of the terms includes the sum of the squares of the coordinates of the radius vector $x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})$ and $y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})$. These are functions of time, but we assumed at the beginning that t is a non-negative variable. As we demonstrated in the previous section, the formula for the initial value may return $t_n = 0$ when $\omega = 0$ and $n = 1$. In this case $\Delta\phi_m = \text{undefined}$. To avoid this case, we can place the entire denominator as an argument of the eliminative function.

$$\Delta\phi_m = \arccos \frac{y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + |x_l x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|}{E(\sqrt{(y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + x_l^2)(x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2 + y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})^2))}), \quad (3.1.8)$$

Note: For better readability, we will not substitute the vector coordinates with their formulas and will remove the upper right index in the notation of the eliminative function. From now on, the basic reducing functions will be written without it.

The formula for $\Delta\phi_m$ includes the first two steps and half of the third step of the angular algorithm: obtaining the input value $t_{[n;m-1]}$, converting it into the coordinates of the spiral vector, and calculating the magnitude of the rotation angle relative to the vertical line.

Knowing how much the radius vector needs to rotate, it remains to determine the direction. In *Figure 16*, it is evident that the direction should be clockwise - meaning backward in time. In the following images, we will demonstrate various configurations of the spiral and line parameters and the direction of rotation they determine.

Figure 17

Figure 18

Figure 19

Figure 20

As can be seen, the direction of the radius vector's rotation depends on the signs of the angular velocity, the point where the vertical line is positioned, and the y -coordinate of the incoming radius vector. *Figure 21* presents a table with the signs of these parameters from the four images above and the sign of $\Delta\phi_m$. The signs are represented as coefficients 1 and -1.

Table of Signs

	ω	x_l	$y_s(t)$	$\Delta\phi$
Fig. 17	1	-1	1	1
Fig. 18	-1	-1	1	-1
Fig. 19	1	-1	-1	-1
Fig. 20	-1	1	-1	-1

Figure 21

The coefficient of the last column $\Delta\phi$ indicates whether the angle (time interval) must be added (1) or subtracted (-1) from the angle (moment of time) of the input radius vector. The coefficient for $\Delta\phi$ can be determined as a function of ω , x_l and $y_s(t)$ - specifically, as the product of the three parameters taken with the opposite sign. Here, it is necessary to use one of the previously defined reduction functions - the *Sign function*.

Let us recall it:

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee0\vee1]} = \frac{x}{|E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (1.3.28)$$

We will replace the argument x from the original definition with the product of ω , x_l and $y_s(t)$, and we will take this product with the opposite sign.

$$S_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]}))} = \frac{-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})}{|E_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})})|}. \quad (3.1.9)$$

At $x_l = 0$, the function will return 0. In this case, the vertical line coincides with the ordinate axis, and its intersection points coincide with the intersection points of the ordinate axis.

Figure 22

Before introducing the *Sign function* as a coefficient, let's move on to the next step of the algorithm - transforming the angle into time.

Step 4

The time interval Δt_m is obtained by dividing the resulting angle $\Delta \phi_m$ by the angular velocity, which is provided as an argument to the eliminative function.

$$\Delta t_m = \frac{\Delta \phi_m(t_{[n;m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E_{(\omega)}|}. \quad (3.1.10)$$

We introduce the *Sign function* as a coefficient to determine whether the time interval Δt_m will be added or subtracted from the previous one.

$$\Delta t_m = S_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]}))} \frac{\Delta \phi_m(t_{[n;m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E_{(\omega)}|}. \quad (3.1.11)$$

This is the final formula for the magnitude and direction of the time interval for the m -th approximation of the spiral radius vector to its intersection point with the vertical line,

as a function of the previous moment and the parameters of the spiral and the vertical line.

Step 5

The final step of the algorithm is to calculate the m -th approximation by adding (or subtracting) the angular difference to the previous moment. We substitute 3.1.11 into 3.0.6:

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} = t_{[n;m-1]} + \Delta t(t_{[n;m-1]}, v, \omega, k, x_l), \quad (3.0.6)$$

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} = t_{[n;m-1]} + S_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]}))} \frac{\Delta \phi_m(t_{[n;m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E(\omega)|}. \quad (3.1.12)$$

Now, we will present the equation in its pure algebraic form, substituting all algebraic checks and formulas for the spiral's coordinates.

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} = t_{[n;m-1]} - \frac{\omega x_l v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega)}{\left| \omega x_l v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega) \right|^{1-0} \left| \omega x_l v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega) \right|} \cdot \frac{\arccos(v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin^2(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega) + |x_l v t_{[n;m-1]} \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega)|)}{\left| \omega^{1-0} \right| \left(\sqrt{(v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin^2(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega) + x_l^2)(v t_{[n;m-1]} \cos^2(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega) + v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin^2(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega))} \right)^{1-0} \left| \sqrt{(v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin^2(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega) + x_l^2)(v t_{[n;m-1]} \cos^2(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega) + v t_{[n;m-1]} \sin^2(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega))} \right|} \quad (3.1.13)$$

The formula is very long and completely unreadable. This is only the angle-based algorithm, where we introduce the formula for the initial values with only its final result $t_{[n;m-1]}$. Including it in its full algebraic form would make things even worse. Therefore, we will stick to the shortened notation of the functions.

Let us return to the algorithm. In *Figure 16*, we graphically illustrated its first iteration. Now, let us see how it works in the subsequent iterations.

Figure 16

Figure 23

In *Figure 23*, the second iteration of the algorithm $m: 2$ is shown. The green vector (the side b) is the black vector (lying on the side a) from the previous iteration (*Figure 16*). It can be observed that the triangle with sides is no longer a right triangle and radius vector continues to move backward in time.

In the next four images, we will trace the movement of the radius vector as it approaches its intersection with the vertical line. We will remove the labels for the sides and the angle.

Figure 24

Figure 25

Figure 26

Figure 27

In *Figures 24-25*, the next three iterations $m: 3-5$ are shown. The angle of rotation $\Delta\phi_m$

becomes smaller and smaller as the radius vector approaches the vertical line. In *Figure 27*,

we jump directly to the thirteenth iteration, where the algorithm stops. Mathematically, the formula is constructed for an infinite number of iterations, but this is neither feasible for a computer program nor necessary. For practical purposes, it is sufficient to define a precision threshold for the approximations. Here, we have chosen a precision up to the 5th decimal place. As shown on the display to the left, at this iteration, the x -coordinate of the radius vector (*Spiral x*) is equal to 1.99998..., while the vertical line is positioned at $x_l = 2$.

In the next section, we will examine the behavior of the algorithm in various scenarios to assess its performance and identify its limitations. Before that, let us demonstrate with a few examples that the algorithm works for other input values $t_n > 1$, as well as for different initial angles of spiral unwinding, various angular and radial velocities, and different positions of the vertical line.

Figure 28

Figure 29

Figure 30

Figure 31

3.2 Limitations of the Angle-Based Algorithm

In this section, we will examine all scenarios in which the algorithm fails and analyze the reasons behind these failures. Resolving the problematic situations will require modifications and expansions of the initial formula. Everything added to the formula from this point onward is aimed at correcting the errors. Once all errors in the algorithm have been addressed, we will proceed to derive the general formula for the intersection points between a spiral and a straight line of the type $y = ax + b$.

As we will see below, all limitations of the algorithm are tied to the position x_l of the vertical line in relation to the specific configuration of the spiral's parameters - v , ω and k . To ensure the algorithm functions correctly, it is essential to identify these situations through algebraic checks tailored to the parameters of the line and the spiral in each case.

Some of these checks involve complex logic and require deriving advanced reduction functions. We will follow a strategy of deriving these checks algebraically outside the equation and then integrating them into it using their assigned names.

Let us recall the scenario from the previous section, which we used to derive the algorithm.

Figure 32

Let us now explore the outcome when the spiral parameters remain unchanged, but the line is positioned on the opposite side of the x -axis. This situation leads to two possible scenarios.

Figure 33

Figure 34

In *Figure 33*, the algorithm successfully identifies the intersection point on the 11-th iteration. However, in *Figure 34*, we observe that it overshoots the position of the vertical line and "lands" the radius vector near the x -axis (this is not the final iteration of the algorithm, as in this case, the radius vector oscillates infinitely above and below the negative x -axis). To understand why this occurs, let us return to the first iteration.

Figure 35

The red dot, which indicates the position of the radius vector in the first iteration, is located slightly 'behind' the vertical line. The readings on the left show that its x -coordinate ($Spiral\ x: -2.542208\dots$) is slightly greater in absolute value than the position x_l of the line ($x: -2.49$). That is, already in the first iteration, the radius vector has passed the vertical line. From this point onward, the algorithm functions normally and continues to move the vector forward over time. Let's see this in the following images.

Figure 36

Figure 37

The direction of the movement of the radius vector is determined by the *Sign function* from the formula 3.1.12.

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} = t_{[n;m-1]} + S_{(\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]}))} \frac{\Delta \phi_m(t_{[n;m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E(\omega)|}. \quad (3.1.12)$$

With this configuration of the parameters of the spiral and the line, $S_{(\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]}))}$ returns 1, meaning the radius vector moves forward in time.

To correct the behavior of the algorithm in scenarios like this, we need to construct an algebraic check that determines whether the x -coordinate of the radius vector in the current iteration is 'behind' the line. This can be easily verified by taking the sign of the difference between the absolute values of x_l and x_s . We will do this again using the *Sign function*, but this time, we will pass the difference as an argument.

$$S_{(|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)} = \frac{|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|}{|E_{(|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)}|}. \quad (3.2.1)$$

The command that performs the new algebraic check $S_{(|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)}$, placed as a coefficient before the multiplier $\frac{\Delta\phi_m(t_{[n;m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E_{(\omega)}|}$, is as follows:

If:

- The x -coordinate of the radius vector in the current iteration is behind the vertical line (i.e., if it is greater in absolute value), reverse the direction of movement defined by the previous coefficient $S_{(\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)}$.

If:

- The x -coordinate of the radius vector in the current iteration is ahead of the line (i.e., if it is smaller in absolute value), keep the direction of movement as defined by $S_{(\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)}$.

The third case – when $x_s(t_{[n;m-1]}) = x_l$, is more specific. It can only occur when the vertical line coincides with the y -axis. However, this case is accounted for by the coefficient in the first check, which also returns 0.

The fourth case – when $x_s(t_{[n;m-1]}) = x_l$ and the line does not coincide with the y -axis – should theoretically never happen. This is due to two reasons:

1. The intersection point between a spiral curve and a vertical line does not have an analytical solution – this is the very definition of the problem being addressed here.
2. In probability theory, the *Probability Density Function* (PDF) states that the likelihood of a continuous random variable being assigned an exact value tends to zero.

$$P(X = c) = \int_c^c f(x) dx = 0, \quad (3.2.2)$$

where X is the random variable, and c is the arbitrarily chosen value.

In this case, the random variable is $x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})$, and the arbitrarily chosen value is x_l . Then we have:

$$P(x_s(t_{[n;m-1]}) = x_l) = \int_{x_l}^{x_l} x_s(t_{[n;m-1]}) dx = 0, \quad (3.2.3)$$

where we have replaced the integrable function $f(x)$ with $x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})$, which is the value of the x -coordinate for each specific m -th iteration of the angular algorithm. The question here is how to interpret $x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})$? The *Probability Density Function* works with a random continuous variable. The variable $x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})$, on the other hand, is continuous but not random – it is the result of well-defined algebraic operations from the angular algorithm. Although the algorithm represents a strict sequence of algebraic actions, the parameters with which it operates – v , ω and k – are chosen arbitrarily. In this sense, here we are looking for the *Probability Density Function* of three random continuous variables with respect to a fourth random continuous variable – x_l . And since there is no analytical connection between them, the probability of randomly selecting such values for the spiral

parameters, so that after inputting them into the algorithm, we get another arbitrary value, tends to zero.

This question is very important because it concerns the problem of the existence of strict mathematical foundations for whether the two-dimensional numerical sequence, defined by the angular algorithm, has a limit. From this perspective, we can define the two-dimensional sequence in the following way:

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = t_{[n;m-1]} + S_{(|x_l|-|x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)} S_{(\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})})} \frac{\Delta \phi_m(t_{[n;m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E_{(\omega)}|}. \quad (3.2.4)$$

Since the sequence is two-dimensional, this means that it has multiple limits, each of which represents the m -th approximation of the n -th intersection point of the spiral curve with the vertical line. Since the vertical line intersects the spiral at specific points, this circumstance requires all the individual sequences that make up the two-dimensional sequence to be convergent. From this perspective, we can redefine the goal of the problem as the task of constructing an absolutely convergent two-dimensional numerical sequence. We can define the absolutely convergent two-dimensional numerical sequence as follows:

We will call a two-dimensional sequence absolutely convergent if each of its elements is a convergent sequence. An element of a two-dimensional sequence will be called any sequence with an initial value $t_{[n;0]}$.

More formally:

$$\{t_{[n;m]}\} \text{ is a convergent sequence if } \exists \lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} \text{ such that } \forall n \geq 0, m \geq 0. \quad (3.2.5)$$

Note: We define $n \geq 0$ because later in the exposition we will need to define a zero intersection point n_0 .

Below, we will see that the algorithm does not always reach a specific limit without corrections.

Let us now return to the images to see how the new coefficient $S_{(|x_l|-|x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)}$ works. This time, we will use different values for the spiral's parameters, which will allow for better and clearer visualization of the algorithm. We will choose parameters with the same signs as those in *Figures 36 and 37* but with different values.

Figure 38

With small values of v and ω , and an initial angle with coefficient $k = 0.8$, we observe a highly distorted spiral. The upper figure shows the first iteration of the algorithm. The next two figures display, respectively, the second iteration without the new coefficient (*Figure 39*) and the second iteration with the new coefficient (*Figure 40*). It is evident that, in the latter case, the coefficient indeed reverses the direction of rotation because $|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})| < 0$.

Figure 39

Figure 40

In the figures below, we see that the corrected algorithm successfully accomplishes its task, achieving the specified approximation of five decimal places to the intersection point by the thirteenth iteration.

Figure 41

Figure 42

The behavior of the algorithm is more interesting in the case shown in *Figures 43-46*.

Figure 43

Figure 44

Figure 45

Figure 46

On the first iteration, the radius vector is behind the line, which triggers the reversal of direction by the coefficient $S(|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)$. However, this sends it to the position of the second iteration, where it is already ahead of the line, and the coefficient does not reverse the direction (returns 1). Moving forward, the radius vector jumps to the third iteration, where it is once again behind the line, causing the direction to reverse again. This is the behavior of an oscillating convergent numerical sequence, such as the sequence $a_n = (-1)^n \frac{1}{n}$.

With each subsequent iteration, the angle of rotation becomes smaller, and the radius vector approaches the line. In this specific case, this happens on the fifteenth iteration.

Figure 47

So far, we have observed three different behaviors of the algorithm, resulting in two types of numerical sequences - two monotonic and one oscillating. Next, we should focus on what causes these differences in behavior. They depend on the position of the vertical line relative to the spiral, i.e., on the configuration of the parameters. More specifically, these behaviors are determined by the position of the line relative to two critical points on the spiral curve. These two points will be referred to as the *Point of Maximum Displacement (PMD)* and the *Point of Return (PR)*.

Figure 48

The *Point of Maximum Displacement* is the point on the spiral where one of the coordinates of the radius vector reaches its maximum value relative to another value of the same coordinate. In this case, it refers to *PMD* along the y -coordinate after the first intersection of the radius vector with the ordinate axis. Every point on the spiral curve can be *PMD* relative to another point, with the sole exception of the point at $t = 0$.

The point of maximum displacement cannot be derived analytically, just like any other point on the spiral. Its properties are of critical importance for certain adjustments in the *Length-Based Algorithm*.

The *Point of Return* is the point at which a given coordinate of the radius vector returns to the same value relative to which the *PMD* is referenced.

These two points - their abscissas, to be precise - define three intervals for the position of the vertical line, within which the algorithm exhibits different behaviors.

Table of Intervals

	$(-\infty; x_{pr})$	$(x_{pr}; x_{pmd})$	$(x_{pmd}; 0]$
$S_{(x_l - x_s(t_{[n;m-1]}))}$	1	-1	-1; 1
$\{t_{[n;m]}\}$	Monotonically ↗	Monotonically ↘	Oscillating ~

Figure 49

In the table above, the first row shows the three open intervals defined by the x -coordinates of *PR* and *PMD*. Below them are the values of the coefficient $S_{(|x_l|-|x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)}$ and the corresponding behavior of the numerical sequence.

The intervals in which we examine the behavior of the algorithm are open because, as we demonstrated earlier, the probability of the vertical line's position coinciding exactly with any of the points is zero. The only exception is the origin of the coordinate system 0, where we have a precisely defined value for $\{t_{[n;m]}\}$, in which case the intersection lies on the ordinate, and the algorithm will not start at all.

Now we will demonstrate the other limitations of the angular algorithm. The image below shows a configuration of the parameters of the line and the spiral in which one of the intersection points is missing.

Figure 50

The place where there should be an intersection point is marked with a question mark. The algorithm calculates all other intersection points, but fails with this one because the line intersects the spiral at this point before the spiral has crossed the ordinate axis for the first time. Therefore, for this point, the algorithm does not obtain an initial value for t .

Now, let's "pull" the vertical line further to the right and see what happens.

Figure 51

So far, we have looked at the limitations of the algorithm where the line was a secant to the corresponding turn of the spiral. In the image above, we see that the line is located behind the first turn of the spiral. We also notice that there is an "intersection" point that is computed by the algorithm, but it lies on the abscissa axis. This point is not an actual intersection between the line and the spiral, yet the algorithm still computes it.

Let's take a closer look at what is happening. The following four images show several non-consecutive iterations of the algorithm.

Figure 52

Figure 53

Figure 54

Figure 55

The algorithm starts from the first intersection with the ordinate axis, and by the 18th iteration, it "lands" the radius vector on the abscissa axis. This happens because there is nothing to stop it earlier — the line is not a secant to this particular turn of the spiral. This scenario will occur with all other turns that the line does not intersect.

Figure 56

There is one more problem to address. It concerns the initial angle. In the previous images, the spiral started its expansion with $k = 3$ or 270 degrees. Now, we will choose $k = 0.5$ (45 degrees) and move the line behind the first turn of the spiral again.

Figure 57

In this scenario, we see that the point doesn't even lie on the spiral curve. Here, the algorithm enters an infinite loop between several values.

Important note: The visualization program is set to either stop the iterations of the algorithm when a precision of 5 decimal places is reached, or to terminate if the algorithm reaches 200 iterations. In the above image, we have the second case.

Figure 58

Figure 59

Figure 60

Figure 61

In the very first iteration, the algorithm calculates a negative value for t , meaning it returns a value outside the domain of t . The subsequent iterations represent a "chaotic" oscillation of the radius vector without converging to a specific value for t .

In other words, the numerical sequence generated by the algorithm is not convergent. This is one of the cases mentioned earlier where the two-dimensional numerical sequence is not absolutely convergent.

This behavior of the algorithm can be corrected by introducing an alternative algorithm for finding the intersection point, along with an appropriate algebraic check that "decides" which of the two algorithms to execute, depending on the configuration of the parameters.

4 Length-Based Algorithm

The introduction of another algorithm for finding the intersection point necessitates the expansion of the formula for the two-dimensional sequence through the implementation of an algebraic check. The new algorithm concerns locating the intersection point of the spiral and the line at a position of the spiral's radius vector before its first encounter with the ordinate axis. Since the numbering of intersection points in the angular algorithm starts from 1, and the *Length-Based Algorithm* must locate an intersection point prior to this first point, we must extend the domain of the two-dimensional sequence with respect to the n -th input value to include zero. The *Length-Based Algorithm* will calculate a zero input value, which, for convenience, will be referred to as the zero intersection point, even though it is not an intersection of the spiral with the ordinate.

Therefore, the check we need to construct for the new algorithm must serve as a *switch* that enables the *Length-Based Algorithm* while simultaneously disabling the *Angular-Based Algorithm* under $n = 0$. For $n > 0$, the check performs the reverse operation.

$$NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]} = \frac{n}{E_{(n)}}, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (4.0.1)$$

$$NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]} = 0, \quad n = 0, \quad (4.0.2)$$

$$NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]} = 1, \quad n > 0. \quad (4.0.3)$$

The supplementary function will therefore have the following form:

$$\overline{NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]}} = 1 - \frac{n}{E_{(n)}}, \quad n \geq 0, \quad (4.0.4)$$

$$\overline{NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]}} = 1, \quad n = 0, \quad (4.0.5)$$

$$\overline{NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]}} = 0, \quad n > 0. \quad (4.0.6)$$

Adding the switch to the equation, in a purely schematic form, it will look like this:

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \overline{NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]}} \text{LB-Alg} + NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0,1]} \text{AB-Alg}, \quad n, m \geq 0, \quad (4.0.7)$$

where the abbreviation LB-Alg denotes the length-based algorithm, and AB-Alg refers to the angle-based algorithm, the formula for which we derived in the previous sections.

The command from the switch is as follows:

If:

- $n = 0$ reset the *Angular-Based Algorithm* and activate the length-based one.

If:

- $n > 0$ reset the *Length-Based Algorithm* and activate the angle-based one.

Now we can proceed with constructing the length-based algorithm.

Step 1

The first problem that needs to be addressed is the issue of the input value. To preserve the analytical aspect of the method, the input value must be derived analytically. It is not possible to search for the intersection point of the spiral with the x -axis because the starting angle is not always such that the spiral intersects the x -axis before intersecting the y -axis. The figure below illustrates a spiral with a starting angle of 270 degrees once again.

Figure 62

We must choose the initial value $t_{[0;0]}$ so that the corresponding radius vector is always positioned before (or coincides with) the position of the line. The most convenient approach is to use the position of the line itself, specifically its length. In this case, the tip of the spiral's radius vector with the same length will always be located before or coincide with the position of the line, provided the line intersects the spiral.

In the figure above, we see a line positioned at point $x_l = 2.32$, along with the radius vector of the spiral that matches it in length. It can be seen that the tip of the vector is located before the line, and the angle ϕ is central.

$$\vec{R} = |x_l|, \quad (4.0.8)$$

$$\vec{R}_x = \vec{R} \cos \phi, \quad (4.0.9)$$

$$\vec{R}_x = |x_l| \cos \phi, \quad (4.0.10)$$

$$\vec{R}_x \leq |x_l|, \quad (4.0.11)$$

where \vec{R}_x is the x -coordinate of the radius vector \vec{R} .

The radius vector \vec{R} is the input value for the length-based algorithm, and it is obtained by transforming the length $|x_l|$ into time using the relationship:

$$\vec{R} = vt, \quad (4.0.12)$$

$$|x_l| = vt, \quad (4.0.13)$$

$$t = \frac{|x_l|}{v}, \quad (4.0.14)$$

$$t_{[0;0]} = \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}}. \quad (4.0.15)$$

The last formula expresses the initial moment $t_{[0;0]}$, with the velocity v placed in the denominator as an argument of the *eliminative* function to avoid division by zero since $v \geq 0$.

Step 2

Figure 63 shows the zeroth and first iterations of the *Length-Based Algorithm*.

Figure 63

The green radius vector \vec{R}_0 , is equal in length to the distance between the origin of the coordinate system and the point x_l . The iterative approximation of the radius vector to the intersection point with the line is achieved by extending the green radius vector to its intersection with the line (the blue point on the vertical line in the image), adding the distance Δs , and finding the radius vector corresponding to this length - $\vec{R}_1 = \vec{R}_0 + \Delta s$. The length of this radius vector can be determined using the angle ϕ and the position of the line x_l .

$$\vec{R}_0 + \Delta s = \frac{|x_l|}{\cos\phi}. \quad (4.0.16)$$

The angle ϕ is determined using the coordinates of the initial radius vector \vec{R}_0 .

$$\phi = \arctan\left(\left|\frac{y_s(t_{[0;0]})}{E_{(x_s(t_{[0;0]})})}\right|\right). \quad (4.0.17)$$

Here, we are interested in the magnitude of the angle without its sign, so we take its absolute value. We use $x_s(t_{[0;0]})$ as an argument for the *eliminative* function because when $x_l = 0$, the initial value of $x_s(t_{[0;0]})$ for the algorithm will also be zero.

We substitute ϕ into 4.0.16:

$$\vec{R}_0 + \Delta s = \frac{|x_l|}{\cos(\arctan(\left|\frac{y_s(t_{[0;0]})}{E_{(x_s(t_{[0;0]})})}\right|))}. \quad (4.0.18)$$

Now, we need to transform the obtained length into time.

Step 2

To obtain the time $t_{[0;1]}$ of the first iteration, we need to divide the length $\vec{R}_0 + \Delta s$ by the radial velocity v .

$$t_{[0;1]} = \frac{\vec{R}_0 + \Delta s}{E_{(v)}}. \quad (4.0.19)$$

We will write down the general solution directly:

$$t_{[0;m]} = \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)} \cos(\arctan(\left|\frac{y_s(t_{[0;m-1]})}{E_{(x_s(t_{[0;m-1]})})}\right|))}. \quad (4.0.20)$$

This is the final formula for the *Length-Based Algorithm*. Unlike the angular algorithm, it does not take the radius vector from the previous iteration as an argument, but uses the position x_l on the vertical line and takes the angle of the current radius vector relative to the x -axis. That is, it directly calculates the new value. For this reason, it does not add or subtract time from the previous iteration of the algorithm. This also eliminates the need for an algebraic check for the direction of the next radius vector.

The behavior of the algorithm under the same conditions that required the construction of an algebraic check for the direction of rotation in the angular algorithm is shown in the four figures below.

Figure 64

Figure 65

Figure 66

Figure 67

It can be seen that the radius vector oscillates as it advances towards the intersection point in a completely natural way without requiring corrections through algebraic checks. This is because the length of the new radius vector is equal to the distance from the center of the coordinate system to the intersection point of the line on which the current radius vector lies and the vertical line.

The *Length-Based Algorithm* also solves the problem of the zero intersection point when the initial angle of the spiral is such that the spiral does not intersect the x -axis. The following images show the first iterations of the algorithm with an initial spiral angle of 11.7 degrees.

Figure 68

Figure 69

Figure 70

Figure 71

It should be noted that, since it is a function of x_l , the initial value for the length algorithm is dynamic, unlike the starting points of the angular algorithm, which are static.

In the next section, we will examine the limitations of the algorithm, and we will correct all these limitations by constructing algebraic checks.

4.1 Limitations of the Length-Based Algorithm

Let's recall the schematic formula of the method, including the two algorithms and the algebraic checks.

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0V1]} \text{LB-Alg} + \overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0V1]} \text{AB-Alg}, \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.07)$$

Let's see how it looks in algebraic form.

$$\begin{aligned} \lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = & \left(1 - \frac{n}{E_{(n)}}\right) \left(\frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)} \cos\left(\arctan\left|\frac{y_s(t_{[0;m-1]})}{E_{(x_s(t_{[0;m-1]})})}\right|\right)}\right) \\ & + \left(\frac{n}{E_{(n)}}\right) \left(t_{[n;m-1]} + S_{(|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})|)} S_{(\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})})} \frac{\Delta\phi_m(t_{[n;m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E_{(\omega)}|}\right), \quad n, m \geq 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4.1.1)$$

All adjustments we will introduce to the length algorithm will be placed as coefficients before it in formula 4.0.7. Moving forward, we will use this formula as it is shorter and clearer.

The first constraint we will examine concerns the problem of determining when a zero intersection point should be calculated and when it should not.

For this purpose, in the upcoming images, we will display the equation for the two-dimensional sequence schematically at the top.

Figure 72

In the figure above, the equation is shown as the sum of the two algorithms *LB-Alg* and *AB-Alg*, along with the names of the two algebraic checks – $\tilde{N}Switch$ and *NSwitch*, respectively. The algebraic checks with a result of 1 are marked in green, while those with a result of 0 are marked in red. Which of the two algorithms will execute the formula depends on the product of the algebraic checks placed as factors before it. Above, we see that *LB-Alg* is green because the check $\tilde{N}Switch$ before it is green. Similarly, *AB-Alg* is red because *NSwitch* is red.

If we substitute the results of the algebraic checks into 4.1.1, then we will have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{n, m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n; m]}\} = & 1 \left(\frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)} \cos \left(\arctan \left(\left| \frac{y_s(t_{[0; m-1]})}{E_{(x_s(t_{[0; m-1]})})} \right| \right) \right)} \right) \\
 & + 0 \left(t_{[n; m-1]} + S_{(|x_l| - |x_s(t_{[n; m-1]})|)} S_{(\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n; m-1]})} \frac{\Delta \phi_m(t_{[n; m-1]}, x_l, v, \omega, k)}{|E_{(\omega)}|} \right), \quad n, m \geq 0.
 \end{aligned} \tag{4.1.2}$$

In the next image, we have the opposite situation because we have $n = 1$.

Figure 73

A problem with *LB-Alg* arises when we position the line on the other side of the *x*-axis.

Figure 74

In this configuration, the line is positioned behind the first intersection point of the spiral, and *LB-Alg* could not calculate a zero intersection point. However, it does calculate such a point because $\tilde{NSwitch}$ returns 1, and it operates with the absolute value of x_l . To address this issue, it is necessary to introduce an additional algebraic check as a multiplier in front of it. Its function is to disable the algorithm if the line is located on the opposite side of the first loop of the spiral.

We will call this algebraic check $KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0,1]}$ as it will take the initial angular coefficient k and the position of the vertical line x_l as arguments. It will be a more complex check, as it will need to verify whether the value of k falls within a given interval and simultaneously

check the sign of x_l .

To construct an interval for verification, we need to extend the function of the sign $S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]}$ and compose a product of multiple extended functions $S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]}$. Let us recall the definition.

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{x}{|E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (1.3.28)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > 0, \quad (1.3.29)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = -1, \quad x < 0, \quad (1.3.30)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.31)$$

Defined in this way, the function returns the signs of the argument relative to zero. If we want it to return the signs relative to another number, we can achieve this as follows:

$$S_{(x-a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{x-a}{|E_{(x-a)}|}. \quad (4.1.3)$$

$$S_{(x-a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > a, \quad (4.1.4)$$

$$S_{(x-a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = -1, \quad x < a, \quad (4.1.5)$$

$$S_{(x-a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x = a, \quad (4.1.6)$$

where $a \in \mathbb{R}$.

Now, we need to determine where the initial angle is located relative to the y -axis. For the vertical line, it is sufficient to determine the sign of x_l through an algebraic check. For the coefficient k , it is slightly more complicated to determine on which side of the y -axis it is located due to the domain of definition of k , which accepts only non-negative values - $0 \leq k < 4$. The coefficient k is located to the left of the y -axis when $1 < k < 3$ and to the right of the y -axis when $0 \leq k < 1$ or $3 < k < 4$. For this purpose, we will construct a check that answers the question of whether $1 < k < 3$. We define two separate sign functions, respectively for 1 and 3. The tables below show the values they return in both cases.

Sign of k relative to 1

	$k < 1$	$k = 1$	$k > 1$
$\frac{k-1}{ E_{(k-1)} }$	-1	0	1

Figure 75

Sign of k relative to 3

	$k < 1$	$k = 3$	$k > 3$
$\frac{k-3}{ E_{(k-3)} }$	-1	0	1

Figure 76

To reduce the results of the two checks to two possible outcomes - 1 or 0 - we construct the product of the two checks as follows:

$$K_{((k-1)(k-3))}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{(k-1)(k-3)}{|E_{((k-1)(k-3))}|}}{2} \rfloor. \quad (4.1.7)$$

k relative to ordinate axis

K	$0 \leq k < 1$	$k = 1$	$1 < k < 3$	$k = 3$	$3 < k$
$\left\lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{(k-1)(k-3)}{ E_{((k-1)(k-3))} }}{2} \right\rfloor$	1	0	0	0	1

Figure 77

The table shows that the check $K_{((k-1)(k-3))}^{[0\vee 1]}$ responds negatively (0) to the question of whether $1 < k < 3$ and positively (1) to whether $0 \leq k < 1$ or $3 < k < 4$. For the boundary cases - $k = 1$ and $k = 3$ - the answer is also 0, as the initial angle lies on the ordinate axis. This is an issue we will address later.

After determining through an algebraic check where the initial angle lies in relation to the ordinate axis, the next step is to determine whether the vertical line is on the same side relative to the ordinate. For this purpose, we simply add x_l as a multiplier in the check $K_{((k-1)(k-3))}^{[0\vee 1]}$ and then we have:

$$KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{x_l(k-1)(k-3)}{|E_{(x_l(k-1)(k-3))}|}}{2} \rfloor. \quad (4.1.8)$$

The table below shows the intervals of k and x_l by columns and rows, and in the individual cells, the result of the $KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ check.

kl match

	$0 \leq k < 1$	$k = 1$	$1 < k < 3$	$k = 3$	$3 < k$
$x_l < 0$	0	0	1	0	0
$x_l = 0$	0	0	0	0	0
$x_l > 0$	1	0	0	0	1

Figure 78

Now we will add the check to equation 4.0.7.

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n,m]}\} = \overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{LB-Alg} + \overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{AB-Alg}, \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.1.9)$$

Let's see how the check $KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ works.

Figure 79

KL is red (returns 0) and consequently LB-Alg also returns 0, even though $\tilde{NSwitch}$ is green and returns 1. At the same time, NSwitch is 0 and AB-Alg also returns 0. The result of the equation as a whole is 0, and therefore, the radius vector of the spiral has a length of 0, which is shown by the arrow at the center of the coordinate system.

On the next image, we place the vertical line on the positive side of the abscissa, and we can see that KL is green and returns 1.

Figure 80

Let's look at other scenarios to ensure that KL works correctly. We will choose different values for k and different signs for the angular velocity ω .

Figure 81

Figure 82

Figure 83

Figure 84

Now we will examine the boundary cases $k = 1$ and $k = 3$.

Figure 85

Figure 86

In both cases, the check KL returns 0, and the equation does not trigger $LB-Alg$, even though the line is on the side of the spiral turn. The same situation occurs when the line is on the positive side of the abscissa.

Figure 87

Figure 88

To address this limitation of KL , we will construct an additional complex check. As seen in the images, besides k and x_l , the direction of the spiral's rotation, i.e., the sign of the angular velocity ω , also becomes a factor in these cases. This check will take three arguments and determine based on them whether to trigger $LB-Alg$ or not.

The first task is to identify the cases in which the check should be performed. Since there are two cases - $k = 1$ and $k = 3$ - and they are mutually exclusive, the check should be analogous to the logical operation disjunction and its mathematical counterpart, addition. We will name this check KWL , and schematically, it looks like this:

$$KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]} = (Case1)(ExpressionA) + (Case2)(ExpressionB). \quad (4.1.10)$$

$KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]}$ is a sum of products where the factors $Case1$ and $Case2$ are intended to activate the corresponding term under specific conditions. These conditions are related to the parameter k and occur only when $k = 1$ or $k = 3$. We already have expressions for these cases from the KL check, but in this instance, we need to take their opposite outputs.

$$Case1 = 1 - \frac{k-1}{E_{(k-1)}}, \quad (4.1.11)$$

$$Case2 = 1 - \frac{k-3}{E_{(k-3)}}. \quad (4.1.12)$$

We substitute into 4.1.11 and obtain:

$$KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \left(1 - \frac{k-1}{E_{(k-1)}}\right)(\text{ExpressionA}) + \left(1 - \frac{k-3}{E_{(k-3)}}\right)(\text{ExpressionB}). \quad (4.1.13)$$

The first factor accounts for the cases shown in *Figures 85 and 87*. In *Figure 85*, we have $\omega > 0$ and $x_l < 0$. In *Figure 87*, the opposite situation occurs - $\omega < 0$ and $x_l > 0$. This means that, once again, we need to use the sign function to construct the algebraic check. Since it must account for two separate cases, we will compose a sum once more.

$$\text{ExpressionA} = \frac{S_{(x_l)} - S_{(\omega)}}{E_{(S_{(x_l)} - S_{(\omega)})}} = \frac{\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} - \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}}{E_{\left(\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} - \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}\right)}}. \quad (4.1.14)$$

Expression A

	$\omega < 0$	$\omega = 0$	$\omega > 0$
$x_l < 0$	0	1	1
$x_l = 0$	1	0	1
$x_l > 0$	1	1	0

Figure 89

When the signs are different, *ExpressionA* returns 1. When one of the parameters is equal to zero, the check also returns 1, but these cases are already addressed by other checks in the equation.

Now we need to construct *ExpressionB*. *Figures 85 and 87* illustrate the cases related to it, and from the images, we observe that x_l and ω must have the same signs. Therefore, we simply reverse the sign from the formula for *ExpressionA*.

$$\text{ExpressionB} = \frac{S_{(x_l)} + S_{(\omega)}}{E_{(S_{(x_l)} + S_{(\omega)})}} = \frac{\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} + \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}}{E_{\left(\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} + \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}\right)}}. \quad (4.1.15)$$

Expression B

	$\omega < 0$	$\omega = 0$	$\omega > 0$
$x_l < 0$	1	1	0
$x_l = 0$	1	0	1
$x_l > 0$	0	1	1

Figure 90

With this, the check $KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]}$ is complete. We substitute ExpressionA and ExpressionB into 4.1.14.

$$KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]} = \left(1 - \frac{k-1}{E_{(k-1)}}\right) \left(\frac{\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} - \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}}{E\left(\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} - \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}\right)}\right) + \left(1 - \frac{k-3}{E_{(k-3)}}\right) \left(\frac{\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} + \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}}{E\left(\frac{x_l}{|E_{(x_l)}|} + \frac{\omega}{|E_{(\omega)}|}\right)}\right). \quad (4.1.16)$$

The addition of this check to the two-dimensional sequence should occur as a summand in a general check along with KL .

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \overline{NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0V1]}} \left(KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]} + KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0V1]}\right) \text{LB-Alg} + NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0V1]} \text{AB-Alg}, \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.1.17)$$

Next, we need to test how KWL functions and how the entire $(KWL + KL)$ check operates as a whole. We will present the same scenarios from *figures 85-88*, but now with the added check.

Figure 91

Figure 92

Figure 93

Figure 94

Finally, let's ensure that KWL returns zero in the cases of $k \neq 1$ and $k \neq 3$.

Figure 95

Figure 96

The correct operation of the $(KWL + KL)$ check leads us to the next issue, which cannot be resolved by it. The image below illustrates a situation where it correctly triggers $LB-Alg$, but the vertical line is not a secant to the spiral in this segment.

Figure 97

Here, the checks before $LB-Alg$ 'decide' to start the algorithm, and it calculates an initial radius vector with a length equal to $|x_l|$. This, in turn, leads to 'chaotic' behavior, resulting in the appearance of points that are not intersection points of the vertical line. The next few images illustrate this 'incorrect' behavior of the algorithm.

Figure 98

Figure 99

Figure 100

Figure 101

The first part of solving this problem consists of restricting the calculation of a zero point to values of $t_{[0;0]}$ where it is either before or coincides with the *Point of Maximum Displacement*. This is related to finding *PMD*. Below, we see how this should look.

Figure 102

Figure 103

The check that we will define in the next section will once again be placed as a factor in front of *LB-Alg* and will disable the algorithm if the vertical line is positioned in such a way that the corresponding radius vector of the spiral lies beyond *PMD*. To achieve this, we need to define the concept of the derivative of a parametric Archimedean spiral.

4.2 Derivatives of an Archimedean Spiral

The parameterization of the Archimedean spiral allows for the definition of three derivatives at each of its points: one derivative $\frac{dy}{dx}$ that is tangent to the spiral curve itself, and two other derivatives - $\frac{dx}{dt}$ and $\frac{dy}{dt}$ - that are tangent to its x - and y -components, respectively.

Let's plot a spiral with parameters $v = 0.5$, $\omega = 1$ and $k = 0.75$

Figure 104

In the image above, all three derivatives are shown at a point on the spiral corresponding to the moment $t = 9.44$ and coordinates $x_s = -1.73968$ and $y_s = -4.38770$. As can be seen, the green line $\frac{dy}{dx}$ is tangent to the spiral curve at this point with a slope of -27.674758 degrees, while the slopes of the other two are 76.617982 ($\frac{dx}{dt}$) and -65.599914 ($\frac{dy}{dt}$). To verify that $\frac{dx}{dt}$ and $\frac{dy}{dt}$ are indeed the derivatives of their respective components, we will present the same situation in a different coordinate system. We will refer to this coordinate system as the txy -diagram or, for brevity, simply t -diagram.

The graphs of the components of the parameterized Archimedean spiral represent sinusoids with increasing amplitude, as it is a combination of rotational motion with constant angular velocity and a linear increase of the radius vector.

Figure 105

On the abscissa, we have the values of t ($t \geq 0$), while on the ordinate, we have the values

of x_s and y_s . The black radius vector represents the radius vector of the spiral at the corresponding moment t . The green line, connecting the tip of the radius vector to the center of the coordinate axis, represents the growth of the radius vector as a function of time. The red sinusoid represents the values of the x -coordinate of the radius vector from the initial moment $t = 0$ to the current one. Similarly, the blue sinusoid represents the values of the y -coordinate. The derivatives $\frac{dx}{dt}$, $\frac{dy}{dt}$ and $\frac{dy}{dx}$ are the straight lines in the respective component colors, and the points indicate the exact positions of the tangents.

In the t -diagram, the derivative $\frac{dy}{dx}$ is not visualized as a tangent to the spiral curve because the spiral curve is decomposed into its components. In the normal coordinate system, only this derivative appears as a tangent, while the other two do not.

Let us now derive the first derivatives of the components of the parameterized Archimedean spiral.

$$x_s(t) = v t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), \quad (4.2.1)$$

$$x'_s(t) = v \left(\cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right), \quad (4.2.2)$$

$$y_s(t) = v t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), \quad (4.2.3)$$

$$y'_s(t) = v \left(\sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + \omega t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right). \quad (4.2.4)$$

Having the derivatives of the components, we derive the derivative $\frac{dy}{dx}(t)$ (the tangent to the spiral curve) as the ratio $\frac{y'(t)}{x'(t)}$.

$$\frac{dy}{dx}(t) = \frac{y'(t)}{x'(t)}, \quad x'(t) \neq 0, \quad (4.2.5)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx}(t) = \frac{\sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + \omega t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t)}{\cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t)}, \quad \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \neq 0. \quad (4.2.6)$$

In its current form, the derivative $\frac{dy}{dx}(t)$ is undefined at $x'(t) = 0$. However, this does not correctly reflect the situation, because the tangent to the spiral curve exists in these cases. In the image below, we see a spiral with the same parameters as the one in the previous images, but it is "reversed" back to moment $t = 8.36565$.

Figure 106

The visualization program correctly represents the derivative $\frac{dy}{dx}(t)$ as a vertical line, but this is due to the fact that it calculates using approximations. In this specific situation $x'(t) = -2.2199526891863997e - 05$, is very close to zero and $\frac{dy}{dx}(t) = 379521.88\dots$. If we convert this value into an angle, we get a value very close to $\frac{\pi}{2}$.

$$\arctan(379521.88\dots) \approx 1.5707936\dots \quad (4.2.7)$$

To avoid a division by zero error in the program, we will place $x'(t)$ in an eliminative function.

$$\frac{dy}{dx}(t) = \frac{y'(t)}{E(x'(t))}, \quad (4.2.8)$$

$$\frac{dy}{dx}(t) = y'(t), \quad x'(t) = 0. \quad (4.2.9)$$

To verify this, we will select parameters for the spiral where the derivative $x'(t) = 0$. It is enough to choose $t = 0$ and $k = 1$. When $t = 0$, the derivative is equal to the cosine of the initial angle multiplied by v .

$$x'(0) = v \cos\left(k \frac{\pi}{2}\right). \quad (4.2.10)$$

Then, if $k = 1$, the cosine is equal to zero.

In the image below, we can see that indeed 4.2.10 is true.

Figure 107

Now we will show how we can use the derivatives $x'(t)$ and $y'(t)$ as a reference for the points of maximum displacement.

Figure 108

Figure 109

Figure 110

Figure 111

The point of maximum displacement is the point at which the derivative of the corresponding component changes its sign. For correcting *LB-Alg*, we are interested in the derivative with respect to the x -coordinate. Let's use the scenario from *Figure 110* and place the vertical line at the x -coordinate of *PMD*. In the images below, we will show the slope of the derivatives 'before' and 'after' *PMD*.

Figure 112

Figure 113

In the next section, we will use derivatives to construct an algebraic check to determine whether the vertical line is positioned behind a given coil of the spiral.

4.3 Sign Change Derivative Detector

To construct the algebraic check needed for correcting *LB-Alg* in cases where the vertical line does not intersect the first turn of the spiral, we will use the sign change of the derivative $x'(t)$. For clarity, we will call this check the *Sign Change Derivative Detector*, although what it will actually check is whether the signs of two variables are the same. We have already used such a check once as part of the more complex check *KWL*, and that was *ExpressionB*. Let's recall *ExpressionB*.

$$\text{ExpressionB} = \frac{S(x_l) + S(\omega)}{E(S(x_l) + S(\omega))} = \frac{\frac{x_l}{|E(x_l)|} + \frac{\omega}{|E(\omega)|}}{E\left(\frac{x_l}{|E(x_l)|} + \frac{\omega}{|E(\omega)|}\right)}. \quad (4.1.16)$$

This check answers the question "Are the signs of x_l and ω the same?" If they are the same, it returns a positive response with one. Let's recall the other outputs as well.

Expression B

	$\omega < 0$	$\omega = 0$	$\omega > 0$
$x_l < 0$	1	1	0
$x_l = 0$	1	0	1
$x_l > 0$	0	1	1

Figure 90

As we can see, the answer is 1 if one of the signs is 0. However, if both are 0, the answer is 0. Further down, we will see that this case will not occur, so it is not problematic.

To construct $\text{SCDD}_{(a,b)}^{[0 \vee 1]}$ (*Sign Change Derivative Detector*) we will simply pass different values into *ExpressionB* as arguments.

$$\text{SCDD}_{(f'_a(t), f'_b(t))}^{[0 \vee 1]} = \frac{\frac{f'_a(t)}{|E(f'_a(t))|} + \frac{f'_b(t)}{|E(f'_b(t))|}}{E\left(\frac{f'_a(t)}{|E(f'_a(t))|} + \frac{f'_b(t)}{|E(f'_b(t))|}\right)}. \quad (4.3.1)$$

Now, we need to find which are the derivatives $f'_a(t)$ and $f'_b(t)$. Let's visualize a vertical line that is tangent to the first spiral turn.

Figure 114

The derivative $f'_b(t)$ is the red line at the black point - i.e., the input value for *LB-Alg*. Its slope is positive because it is located "before" *PMD* and the x -coordinate of the spiral vector is increasing. The sign of this derivative will be compared with the sign of $f'_a(0)$, which is the derivative at the moment $t = 0$ and is located at the origin of the coordinate system. The derivative $f'_a(0)$ at this exact moment is the only possible reference point for comparison, as it is simultaneously before *PMD* and before the input for *LB-Alg*.

Now, we need to define $f'_a(t)$ and $f'_b(t)$. As we showed in the previous section, the derivative $x'_s(0)$ of the x -component of the spiral at the moment $t = 0$ is equal to the cosine of the initial angle multiplied by v .

$$x'_s(0) = v \cos\left(k \frac{\pi}{2}\right). \quad (4.2.10)$$

$$f'_a(0) = x'_s(0) = v \cos\left(k \frac{\pi}{2}\right). \quad (4.3.2)$$

Similarly, $f'_b(t)$ is the derivative of the x -component at the initial moment $t_{[0,0]}$. This is the initial moment we derived as a function of the position x_l of the vertical line and it is the fundamental formula for *LB-Alg*. Let us recall the formula:

$$t_{[0,0]} = \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}}. \quad (4.0.15)$$

We pass $t_{[0,0]}$ as an argument to the derivative $x'(t)$.

$$f'_b(t_{[0;0]}) = x'_s(t_{[0;0]}) = v \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{[0;0]}) - \omega t_{[0;0]} \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{[0;0]}) \right), \quad (4.3.3)$$

$$x'_s(t_{[0;0]}) = v \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) - \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)} \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) \right). \quad (4.3.4)$$

We substitute in 4.3.1 and obtain the final formula for the *SCDD*-check.

$$\text{SCDD}_{(x'_s(0), x'_s(t_{[0;0]}))}^{[0V1]} = \frac{\frac{v \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2})}{|E(v \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2}))|} + \frac{v \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) - \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)} \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) \right)}{\left| v \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) - \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)} \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) \right) \right|}}{E \left(\frac{\frac{v \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2})}{|E(v \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2}))|} + \frac{v \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) - \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)} \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) \right)}{\left| v \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) - \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)} \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}) \right) \right|}} \right)} \quad (4.3.5)$$

Before adding it as a multiplier in front of *LB-Alg*, let's once again show which scenarios the *SCDD*-check should prevent.

Figure 115

In this situation, the vertical line is in a position where its corresponding radius vector, in terms of length, is located after *PMD*. As seen, the derivative $x'_s(t_{[0;0]})$ at this point has a negative sign, while the derivative $x'_s(0)$ has a positive sign. Now, we apply the *SCDD*-check as a coefficient and obtain:

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \overline{\text{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0V1]}} \text{SCDD}_{(x'_s(0), x'_s(t_{[0;0]}))}^{[0V1]} \left(\text{KWL}_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]} + \text{KL}_{(k,x_l)}^{[0V1]} \right) \text{LB-Alg} + \text{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0V1]} \text{AB-Alg}, \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.3.6)$$

Here is how *SCDD* works. The same scenario from *Figure 115*, with the visualizations of the derivatives included. The check returns 0, *LB-Alg* is also zero, and the final result for the sequence boundary at $n = 0$ is zero.

Figure 116

The next two images show the boundary case where $SCDD$ returns 1. This happens when the vertical line is in a position x_l where the initial radius vector lies exactly on PMD . A slight change in x_l and $SCDD$ returns 0.

Figure 117

Figure 118

$SCDD$ however has limitations. One of them is visible in *Figure 117*. Slightly above the black point -where the tip of the initial radius vector is located - there is another point, purple, which should not be there. It is not an intersection point of the spiral and the line. Let's track the iterations of the algorithm to see that it indeed places an intersection point there on the 199-th iteration.

Figure 119

Before solving this problem, we will address another issue. Since *SCDD* compares the signs of derivatives, it will return 1 in all cases where the signs are the same. Such a case is shown in the figure below, where the vertical line is in a position where its corresponding radius vector has a derivative with the same sign as the derivative at $t = 0$.

Figure 120

The tip of this radius vector is located slightly after *PMD*, and accordingly, its derivative is positive. The solution to this problem is to introduce a restriction on the cases where the algorithm calculates a zero intersection point. This restriction will set a maximum allowable value for the position of the vertical line at which a zero intersection point can be computed.

We will call this new check *X Maximum Distance (XMD)*, and it will verify whether the absolute value of x_l is less than a specified threshold. We will choose this threshold to

be the length of the radius vector at its first intersection with the ordinate axis.

Figure 121

For this specific spiral on the image above, this value is 1.570796.... The *XMD* check is defined as follows:

$$\text{XMD}_{(x_l, y_s(t_{[1;0]}))}^{[0\vee 1]} = \left\lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{|y_s(t_{[1;0]})| - |x_l|}{E^{(|y_s(t_{[1;0]})| - |x_l|)}}}{2} \right\rfloor. \quad (4.3.7)$$

X Maximum Distance

	$ y_s(t_{[1;0]}) > x_l $	$ y_s(t_{[1;0]}) \leq x_l $
$\left\lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{ y_s(t_{[1;0]}) - x_l }{E^{(y_s(t_{[1;0]}) - x_l)}}}{2} \right\rfloor$	1	0

Figure 122

Since the radius vector we use as a constraint lies on the ordinate axis, its length is equal to its *y*-component at the moment $t_{[1;0]} = 1.570796\dots$

$$y_s(t_{[1;0]}) = vt_{[1;0]} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{[1;0]}\right) \quad (4.3.8)$$

The moment $t_{[1;0]}$ will be found using formula 2.2.28.

$$t_n = \frac{\pi \left(\text{Greater}_{(\omega)}^{[0\vee 1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + \text{Less}_{(\omega)}^{[0\vee 1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- + (n-1) \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1\vee \omega]}|}. \quad (2.2.22)$$

By setting $n = 1$ and $t_1 = t_{[1;0]}$ we obtain:

$$t_{[1;0]} = \frac{\pi \left(\text{Greater}_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + \text{Less}_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}. \quad (4.3.9)$$

We will leave the equation for XMD in the form of formula 4.3.7 since substituting $t_{[1;0]}$ would make it difficult to read and write.

Let's add XMD to the equation and return to the situation from *Figure 120* to see how it works.

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0V1]} XMD_{(x_l, y_s(t_{[1;0]}))}^{[0V1]} SCDD_{(x'_s(0), x'_s(t_{[0;0]}))}^{[0V1]} \left(KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]} + KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0V1]} \right) \text{LB-Alg} + NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0V1]} \text{AB-Alg}, \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.3.10)$$

Figure 123

Although $SCDD$ returns 1, XMD returns 0 and correctly 'turns off' $LB-Alg$.

The first problem we mentioned earlier from *Figure 119* concerns the process of iterative approximation. In this scenario, the vertical line does not intersect the spiral in its specific turn, but $LB-Alg$ computes a zero intersection point, which triggers further iteration.

This undesired behavior of the algorithm can be corrected by constructing another check that also uses the derivative $x'_s(t)$, but this time verifying its value at each iteration. This check is fundamentally the same as $SCDD$, with the difference that instead of comparing the current derivative with the derivative $x'_s(t)$ at $t = 0$, it will compare it with the derivative at the initial value from which the iterative process begins. To distinguish it from the first $SCDD$ check, we will call it *Iteration Start Sign Change Derivative Detector* or $ISSCDD$.

$$\text{ISSCDD}_{(x'_s(t_{[n;0]}), x'_s(t_{[n;m]}))}^{[0\vee 1]} = \frac{\frac{x'_s(t_{[n;0]})}{|E_{(x'_s(t_{[n;0]})})|} + \frac{x'_s(t_{[n;m]})}{|E_{(x'_s(t_{[n;m]})})|}}{E\left(\frac{x'_s(t_{[n;0]})}{|E_{(x'_s(t_{[n;0]})})|} + \frac{x'_s(t_{[n;m]})}{|E_{(x'_s(t_{[n;m]})})|}\right)}, \quad (4.3.11)$$

The first is that this check must be performed not only for the zero initial "intersection" point but for every n -th intersection point. In other words, this check will be carried out for the iterations of *LB-Alg* as well as for *AB-Alg*. Later, we will see why this is necessary when addressing one of the final issues of the algorithm.

Second, the moment $t_{[n;m]}$ at which we will check the sign of the derivative $x'_s(t_{[n;m]})$ is actually the result of the algorithm's operation rather than just an input value. This means that the formula enters recursion - the result of the current iteration is simultaneously an input parameter.

In other words, the formula calculates the derivative at the current m -th iteration, compares its sign with the sign of the derivative at the initial moment, and if they are different, it nullifies the result computed by itself. If the signs are the same, it continues iterating forward until the intersection point is reached with the chosen level of accuracy.

Since this check will be executed for both algorithms, it requires *ISSCDD* to be placed as a multiplier in front of the entire formula. Here is how its addition will look:

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \text{ISSCDD}_{(x'_s(t_{[n;0]}), x'_s(t_{[n;m]}) \rightarrow)}^{[0\vee 1]} \left(\overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{XMD}_{(x_l, y_s(t_{[1;0]}))}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{SCDD}_{(x'_s(0), x'_s(t_{[0;0]}))}^{[0\vee 1]} \right. \\ \left. \left(\text{KWL}_{(k, w, x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} + \text{KL}_{(k, x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} \right) \text{LB-Alg} + \text{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{AB-Alg} \right), \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.3.12)$$

The entry into recursion is indicated in the formula through the arguments we pass to the new check *ISSCDD*- namely, $x'_s(t_{[n;0]})$ and $x'_s(t_{[n;m]})$.

Important note: $x'_s(t_{[n;m]})$ is the value computed from the formula located inside the parentheses following *ISSCDD*, i.e., the formula 4.3.10 before we add *ISSCDD*. This is indicated by the arrow ' \rightarrow ' after the argument $x'_s(t_{[n;m]})$ passed into *ISSCDD*.

Let's now take a closer look at how this check works. We will use the same spiral parameters as in *Figure 119* but position the line slightly to the left so that it does not intersect the spiral, while the initial vector of the zero point remains before *PMD*.

First, we will examine what happens during the first four iterations without the new check.

Figure 124

Figure 125

Figure 126

Figure 127

The initial derivative $x'_s(t_{[n;0]})$ (in this scenario $x'_s(t_{[0;0]})$) is at the point of the initial radius vector and has a positive x -derivative's slope. We compare the derivative $x'_s(t_{[n;m]})$ ($x'_s(t_{[0;m]})$) against it.

On the third iteration $m = 3$, the derivative $x'_s(t_{[0;2]})$ (Figure 126) changes its sign, and its slope becomes negative. Despite this, the process continues (Figure 127).

Now we will add *ISSCDD* and run the same scenario.

Figure 128

Figure 129

Figure 130

Figure 131

During the first two iterations - *Figures 128 and 129* - *ISSCDD* returns 1 and executes *LB-Alg*. On the third iteration - *Figure 130* - the x -derivative is already negative, *ISSCDD* returns 0, stops the execution of *LB-Alg*, and computes a radius vector with a length of 0, where its x -derivative is the same as the x -derivative at $t = 0$.

Note: In *Figure 130*, a green radius vector is shown, whose extension to the vertical line is the blue point. This is not the current radius vector but the radius vector from the previous iteration, i.e., the black radius vector from *Figure 129*.

Since we defined *ISSCDD* as a check applicable to every n -th intersection point, let's verify whether it works correctly in these cases as well. In the images below, we will track what happens if $n = 1$.

Figure 132

Figure 133

Figure 134

Figure 135

At $n = 1$, the equation activates *AB-Alg* instead of *LB-Alg*. The x -derivative of the initial radius vector (*Figure 132*) is negative. We skip two iterations, and in *Figures 133 and 134* we jump directly to the fourth and fifth iterations ($m = 4, m = 5$), where the derivative angle approaches 180 degrees. In *Figure 135*, the algorithm has moved the radius vector to a position below *PMD*, where its derivative is now positive. *ISSCDD* detects this and, by returning zero, deactivates *AB-Alg*. The result is once again a radius vector with zero length.

After implementing these corrections, we move on to the next issues of the algorithm.

4.4 Last two problems

Two issues remain to be corrected. The first one was already presented in section 4.1 *Limitations of the Angle-Based Algorithm*. It concerned the behavior of the angular

algorithm for spiral turns that the vertical line does not intersect. The problem was that the angular algorithm lands the radius vector onto the x -axis.

Figure 136

Here, we need to make an important clarification about which radius vectors are being landed onto the x -axis. Since we have already added the *ISSCDD*-check, we will see that it deactivates *AB-Alg* in some cases but not in others. In the two images below, we show the first initial radius vector and the final radius vector at the 5-th intersection point.

Figure 137

Figure 138

As can be seen, the derivatives have the same sign (positive slope) at the beginning and at the end of the iterative process, and *ISSCDD* gives a "green light" for *AB-Alg*. However, the situation is different for the intersection points on the positive side of the ordinate axis.

Figure 139

Figure 140

In this case, on the third iteration ($m = 3$), the derivative changes its sign, and *ISSCDD* nullifies *AB-Alg*. These behaviors of the algorithm are due to the position of *PMD*. In the upper case, the "descending" radius vector passes *PMD*, causing the derivative to change its sign. In the previous case, *PMD* is positioned above the x -axis (i.e., after it in terms of time t), which is why the derivative does not change its sign.

This is a problem for which we will define a check whose role is to prevent the start of *AB-Alg* under certain conditions. We will leave this for last. Before that, we will address and solve the other problem shown in the image below.

Figure 141

The vertical line is positioned between *PMD* and the intersection point of the spiral with the x -axis, and *AB-Alg* cannot move the radius vector from any of the initial vectors. In one case - *Figure 142* - at $n = 1$, the radius vector lands on the x -axis, while in the other - *Figure 143*, it reaches the intersection point with the line.

Figure 142

Figure 143

This problem is the same as the missing point issue occurring at $n = 0$, with the difference that it appears for $n > 0$. The solution is the same - using *LB-Alg*. This means that it should be added as a third term to the equation for the two-dimensional sequence, with the necessary checks as multipliers in front of it.

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \text{ISSCDD}_{(x'_s(t_{[n;0]}), x'_s(t_{[n;m]})) \rightarrow}^{[0\vee 1]} \left(\overline{NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} XMD_{(x_l, y_s(t_{[1;0]})}^{[0\vee 1]}} SCDD_{(x'_s(0), x'_s(t_{[0;0]})}^{[0\vee 1]}} \right. \\ \left. \left(KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} + KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} \right) \text{LB-Alg} + NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \right. \\ \left. \left(\overline{XYSwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{AB-Alg} + XYSwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{LB-Alg}} \right) \right), \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.4.1)$$

Since this *LB-Alg* occurs at $n > 0$, we place both algorithms in parentheses before $NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]}$, with the additional condition $XYSwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]}$ as a switch before each algorithm, ensuring that only one of them operates at a time.

Two problems need to be solved here - the first is defining *XYSwitch*, and the second is providing an initial value for *LB-Alg*, since the conditions for its activation differ slightly from the case of the zero intersection point.

The new check should determine a specific range of values for the position of the vertical line. If the line is within this range, it should return 1; otherwise, it should return 0. In *Figure 142*, we can see that the line is positioned slightly after the intersection of the spiral with the x -axis, where *LB-Alg* grounds the radius vector for the corresponding coil, in this case, $n = 1$. The intersection point of the spiral with the x -axis will serve as the lower boundary. As the upper boundary, we will take the length of the radius vector at the point where the spiral intersects the next coordinate axis, i.e., the y -axis.

Figure 144

If we look at the values of the lower and upper boundaries from *Figures 142 and 144*, we will see that x_l is positioned between them - $-0.63617... < -0.437 < -0.42403...$ (Spiral $y < x < \text{Spiral } x$ on the images).

Here is how the interval looks.

Figure 145

The check must determine whether the line is within this interval and on the same side of the spiral turn. The latter is necessary because the line could be positioned on the other side of the x -axis, in which case the check would also return 1.

Therefore, $XYSwitch$ represents the product of two checks.

$$XYSwitch_{(x_l, x_s, y_s)}^{[0V1]} = (XBetween)(Xsigns), \quad (4.4.2)$$

where $XBetween$ checks the interval, and $XSigns$ checks the signs of x_l and x_s .

We have already performed an interval check once before - the KL check.

$$KL_{(k, x_l)}^{[0V1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{x_l(k-1)(k-3)}{|E_{(x_l(k-1)(k-3))}|}}{2} \rfloor. \quad (4.1.9)$$

The $XBetween$ check examines the relationship between three lengths and determines whether one of them - x_l is positioned between the other two, namely between x_s and y_s . For this purpose, we rewrite the KL check as follows:

$$XBetween_{(x_l, x_s, y_s)}^{[0V1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 - \frac{(|x_l| - |x_s|)(|y_s| - |x_l|)}{|E_{((|x_l| - |x_s|)(|y_s| - |x_l|))}|}}{2} \rfloor. \quad (4.4.3)$$

Now we need to define the two radius vectors x_s and y_s . Since we are performing a check related to a specific initial radius vector (in this case, from *Figure 142*, this is the first initial radius vector or y_1), we will use it as a reference point to obtain the lengths of x_s and y_s . These two radius vectors can be obtained by rotating the initial vector by 90 and 180 degrees forward in time, respectively. Purely schematically:

$$x_s = \vec{y}_1 + 90^\circ, \quad (4.4.4)$$

$$y_s = \vec{y}_1 + 180^\circ. \quad (4.4.5)$$

Let's recall how we obtained the initial radius vectors.

$$t_n = \frac{\pi \left(Greather_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- + (n-1) \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}. \quad (2.2.22)$$

Therefore, to obtain the length of the radius vector x_s , we need to add $\frac{\pi}{2}$ radians to the initial angle.

$$t_{n+1/2} = \frac{\pi \left(Greather_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- + (n-1) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}. \quad (4.4.6)$$

For adding an angle of π radians for the next initial radius vector, we will simply take the next initial moment, i.e., $n+1$.

$$t_{n+1} = \frac{\pi \left(Greather_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- + n \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}. \quad (4.4.7)$$

Now, for purely pragmatic reasons, we will change the values we compare in this check, and instead of comparing the lengths x_l , x_s and y_s we will compare their equivalent values in relation to t . To achieve this, we will convert the position of the vertical line x_l into time, and thus for t_{x_l} we have:

$$t_{x_l} = \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}}. \quad (4.4.8)$$

Fewer operations are required to convert the length $|x_l|$ at moment t_{x_l} than to convert the moments $t_{n+1/2}$ and t_{n+1} into the lengths of the radius vectors x_s and y_s using the formulas for the components $x(t_{n+1/2}) = vt_{n+1/2} \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{n+1/2})$ and $y(t_{n+1}) = vt_{n+1} \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{n+1})$. Therefore, for convenience, we adopt the notation $t_{n+1/2}$ for the moment of the radius vector x_s , even though n takes integer values.

Substituting these values into 4.4.3, we obtain:

$$XBetween_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0V1]} = \left\lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{(\frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}} - t_{n+1/2})(t_{n+1} - \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}})}{|E_{(x_l x(t_{n+1/2}))}|}}{2} \right\rfloor. \quad (4.4.9)$$

Note: Unlike x_l , the moments $t_{n+1/2}$ and t_{n+1} are always positive since the domain of definition of t is $t \geq 0$, so there is no need to take their absolute values. We also change the arguments passed to $XBetween$, replacing x_s and y_s with v , ω and k , as they are the necessary parameters for calculating $t_{n+1/2}$ and t_{n+1} .

With this, the $XBetween$ check is completed, and what remains is to define $XSigns$. Since it needs to determine whether x_l and $x_{t+1/2}$ are on the same side of the x -axis (see *Figure 142*), it will check the sign of the product between them.

$$XSigns_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0V1]} = \left\lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{x_l x(t_{n+1/2})}{|E_{(x_l x(t_{n+1/2}))}|}}{2} \right\rfloor, \quad (4.4.10)$$

$$x(t_n + 1/2) = vt_{n+1/2} \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t_{n+1/2}). \quad (4.4.11)$$

The final step is to substitute the checks *XBetween* and *XSigns* into the formula for *XYSwitch*.

$$XYSwitch_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0 \vee 1]} = \left(\frac{1 + \frac{(\frac{|x_l|}{E(v)} - t_{n+1/2})(t_{n+1} - \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)})}{|E(\frac{(\frac{|x_l|}{E(v)} - t_{n+1/2})(t_{n+1} - \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)})|}}}{2} \right) \left(\frac{1 + \frac{x_l x(t_{n+1/2})}{|E(x_l x(t_{n+1/2}))|}}{2} \right). \quad (4.4.12)$$

The opposite check is therefore:

$$\overline{XYSwitch_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0 \vee 1]}} = 1 - XYSwitch_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0 \vee 1]}. \quad (4.4.13)$$

After defining *XYSwitch*, the remaining task is to resolve the issue with the input value of *LB-Alg*. Let's recall its formula:

$$t_{[0; m]} = \frac{|x_l|}{E(v) \cos(\arctan(|\frac{y_s(t_{[0; m-1]})}{E(x_s(t_{[0; m-1]})})|))}, \quad (4.0.20)$$

where the input value of the algorithm was determined based on the position x_l of the line.

$$t_{[0; 0]} = \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}. \quad (4.0.15)$$

If we use this formula, it will lead to calculating a dynamic input value as long as x_l is within the length interval between y_s and x_s . In the images below, it can be seen that the input value has different lengths, and in *Figure 147*, it moves behind *PMD*.

Figure 146

Figure 147

It is unlikely, but under a certain configuration of the spiral and line parameters, this could still lead to calculating an incorrect 'intersection point.' To avoid such a possible scenario, we will use a different length as the input parameter. This length will remain static for any position of the line. It will be the same radius vector that we used as the upper boundary of the interval in *XYSwitch*.

Figure 148

Figure 149

As can be seen, shifting the line to the same position as in *Figure 147* does not change the initial radius vector.

All this means that we need to redefine *LB-Alg* for each n -th initial radius vector. Then we have:

$$t_{[n;m]} = \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)} \cos(\arctan(|\frac{y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})}{E_{(x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})})}|))}, \quad (4.4.14)$$

where the initial moment $t_{[n;0]} = t_{n+1/2}$ from 4.4.6.

$$t_{[n;0]} = \frac{\pi \left(Greater_{(\omega)}^{[0\vee 1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0\vee 1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- + (n-1) + \frac{\pi}{2} \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1\vee \omega]}|}. \quad (4.4.15)$$

However, the actual initial value is not determined based on the length of the radius vector x_s , but rather on the position x_l . The value of the y -component of this radius vector is 0 (*Figure 148*), which means that the multiplier $\cos(\arctan(|\frac{y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})}{E_{(x_s(t_{[n;m-1]})})}|))$ in the denominator in 4.4.14 equals 1. Then:

$$t_{[n;0]} = \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}}. \quad (4.4.16)$$

This extension of the definition of *LB-Alg* requires giving it a different name when it is executed in cases for $n \geq 1$. We will call it *NLB-Alg*, and thus the formula for the two-dimensional sequence of intersection points will have the following schematic form:

$$\lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = \text{ISSCDD}_{(x'_s(t_{[n;0]}), x'_s(t_{[n;m]}) \rightarrow)}^{[0\vee 1]} \left(\overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{XMD}_{(x_l, y_s(t_{[1;0]})})}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{SCDD}_{(x'_s(0), x'_s(t_{[0;0]})})}^{[0\vee 1]} \right. \\ \left. \left(\overline{KWL}_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} + \overline{KL}_{(k,x_l)}^{[0\vee 1]} \right) \text{LB-Alg} + \overline{NSwitch}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \right. \\ \left. \left(\overline{XYSwitch}_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{AB-Alg} + \overline{XYSwitch}_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{NLB-Alg} \right) \right), \quad n, m \geq 0. \quad (4.4.17)$$

Now, let's return to the scenario from *Figure 148* and see how the new check *XYSwitch* and the algorithm *NLB-Alg* work.

Figure 150

Figure 151

In *Figure 150*, we see that *XYSwitch* activates *NLB-Alg*, *XYSwitch* deactivates *AB-Alg* and moves the initial vector from the positive ordinate axis to the negative abscissa axis. In the other figure, we see that the radius vector in the first iteration ($m = 1$) is longer than the initial vector and has the same length as x_1 .

We will examine another scenario to ensure that all checks, including the new one, function correctly.

Figure 152

Figure 153

In *Figure 152*, we see that *NLB-Alg* is activated for the 6-th initial radius vector, and it is correctly rotated by 90 degrees to the abscissa axis. In the next figure, we see that the line is shifted slightly to the right, where it does not intersect the spiral loop. Here, *ISSCDD* is triggered and disables *NLB-Alg* (as well as all other algorithms) already in the first iteration.

Now that we have corrected this issue in the algorithms, the final problem remains. It can be seen in *Figure 153*. We will display it in a larger size.

Figure 153

The problem lies in the points aligned along the x -axis at the locations where the spiral curve intersects it. For this specific parameters of the spiral and the position of the line, these are the even initial vectors, or those on the positive side of the y -axis. Let's verify that this is indeed the case.

Figure 154

Figure 155

The even initial radius vector $n = 2$ 'lands' on the x -axis at the 11-th iteration.

Figure 156

Figure 157

In contrast to the even radius vector, the odd one $n = 3$ passes through PMD , and $ISSCDD$ resets $AB-Alg$ as early as the second iteration. (The green radius vector in Figure 157)

is the radius vector from the previous iteration).

To get a clearer idea of what the new check should do, let's look at the image below. It shows a spiral and a vertical line that does not intersect the first three coils. On these coils, the algorithm incorrectly positions intersection points on the x -axis. Therefore, the new check must disable the algorithm only for the first three coils, but not for all the others.

Figure 158

This can be achieved if the check verifies whether the line is located behind a specific coil. If it is behind it, it will return 0; if it is in front of it, it will return 1. More specifically, the check will be performed in relation to the intersection point of the spiral with the x -axis.

The new check will be called *ABSwitch*, as its role will be to decide whether to activate *AB-Alg*, i.e., for $n \geq 1$. *LB-Alg* is not involved in these calculations because we have already defined other checks that determine under what conditions it should be activated.

$$\text{ABSwitch}_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0V1]} = \left[\frac{1 + \frac{t_{n \pm 1/2} + C - \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)}}{E(t_{n \pm 1/2} + C - \frac{|x_l|}{E(v)})}}{2} \right]. \quad (4.4.18)$$

Two things need to be explained in this formula. One is the plus-minus sign in $t_{n \pm 1/2}$ and the constant C . The double sign for addition needs to be included because, depending on the number n , either the time $\frac{\pi}{2E(w)}$ needs to be added or the same time needs to be subtracted from the initial vector. The images below illustrate this.

Figure 159

Figure 160

Due to the position of the line on the negative abscissa, the specified time must be added to the time of the initial vector $n = 5$, while for the next initial vector $n = 6$, the same time must be subtracted in order to find the length of the radius vector lying on the abscissa, relative to which we will compare the position of the line x_l . Which of the two operations should be performed will be determined through an algebraic check. Such a check has already been defined in the angular algorithm. This is the sign check from 3.1.9.

$$S_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]}))} = \frac{-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})}{|E_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;m-1]})})|}. \quad (3.1.9)$$

We will slightly modify the formula by replacing $m - 1$ with 0. This gives us:

$$S_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;0]}))} = \frac{-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;0]})}{|E_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;0]})})|}. \quad (4.4.19)$$

For $n = 5$ from *Figure 159*, we add accordingly, while for $n = 6$ from the next figure, we subtract. However, we will perform this check outside the time formula to avoid unnecessary modifications to it. Let us recall once again:

$$t_n = \frac{\pi \left(Greater_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^+ + Less_{(\omega)}^{[0V1]} \Delta\theta(k)^- + (n - 1) \right)}{2|E_{(\omega)}^{[1V\omega]}|}. \quad (2.2.22)$$

With the addition of the check, the formula 4.4.18 takes the form:

$$ABS_{switch}_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0V1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{t_{[n;0]} + S_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;0]})}) \frac{\pi}{2E_{(\omega)}} + C - \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}}}{E_{\left(t_{[n;0]} + S_{(-\omega x_l y_s(t_{[n;0]})}) \frac{\pi}{2E_{(\omega)}} + C - \frac{|x_l|}{E_{(v)}} \right)}}}{2} \rfloor. \quad (4.4.20)$$

The constant C is a number that we introduce to ensure that the interval is large enough to include the x -coordinate of the point of maximum displacement. In the above scenario, the odd initial vectors land on the abscissa before it, while the even ones do not. We will choose the number $\frac{\pi}{4E_{(\omega)}}$ as the value of the constant, which corresponds to an angular displacement of 45 degrees. Adding it to the length of the rotated radius vector guarantees that the x -coordinate of PMD is included within it.

$$C = \frac{\pi}{4E_{(\omega)}}. \quad (4.4.21)$$

In the image below, the red point is the boundary for the two initial vectors - $n = 5$ and $n = 6$ - beyond which the algorithms should not calculate an intersection points.

Figure 161

Now we will add the check *ABSwitch* to the equation.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \lim_{n,m \rightarrow \infty} \{t_{[n;m]}\} = & \text{ISSCDD}_{(x'_s(t_{[n;0]}), x'_s(t_{[n;m]} ->))}^{[0V1]} \left(\overline{NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0V1]} XMD_{(x_l, y_s(t_{[1;0]})}^{[0V1]} SCDD_{(x'_s(0), x'_s(t_{[0;0]})}^{[0V1]} \right. \\
 & \left. \left(KWL_{(k,w,x_l)}^{[0V1]} + KL_{(k,x_l)}^{[0V1]} \right) \text{LB-Alg} \right. \\
 & \left. + NSwitch_{(n)}^{[0V1]} \left(\overline{XYSwitch_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0V1]} ABSwitch_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0V1]} \text{AB-Alg} \right. \right. \\
 & \left. \left. + XYSwitch_{(x_l, v, \omega, k)}^{[0V1]} \text{LB-Alg} \right) \right), \quad n, m \geq 0. \tag{4.4.22}
 \end{aligned}$$

Let's check how it works.

Figure 162

Figure 163

We see that, in fact, *ABSwitch* disables *AB-Alg* not only for the 5-th and 6-th initial vectors but also for all before them, as their boundaries are far before the boundary of the mentioned initial vectors. The intersection points on the abscissa for all spiral turns before the 7-th have been removed.

The two images below show the 7-th and 8-th initial vectors, and we see that *AB-Alg* is enabled since the line is located before their boundaries.

Figure 164

Figure 165

With this, the corrections in the algorithms are complete. Formula 4.4. is the final formula for the two-dimensional numerical sequence of intersection points between a vertical line and a spiral with arbitrary parameters. The two-dimensional numerical sequence is absolutely convergent, according to the definition we introduced - all individual sequences that compose it have a limit. These limits are of two types: one type consists of the intersection points between the spiral and the vertical line, and the other is the origin of the coordinate system (0;0), where the algorithms land the radius vector of the spiral in cases where they would otherwise compute an incorrect intersection point.

In the next section, we will move on to the problem of finding the intersection between a spiral and a line with an arbitrary slope.

5 General solution for a line with a slope

In general, the strategy for finding the intersection points between an Archimedean spiral and a line with a slope consists of reducing the situation to the corresponding situation for a vertical line. In the image below, we have a spiral with an initial angle of 0 degrees and an inclined line with a slope $a = -1$ (-45 degrees) and a constant $b = 1$. In the annotations, we also have $x = 0.70711$, whose value in this case is not the intersection point of the line with the x -axis but rather the distance from the center to the inclined line. Below, we will illustrate this.

Figure 166

We will show that this situation is analogous to the one in the image below, where the distance from the center of the coordinate system to the position of the vertical line is also $x = 0.70711$, but the initial angle of the spiral is rotated by 45 degrees in the negative direction (clockwise), or as seen in the annotations – 315 degrees.

Figure 167

The solution, therefore, is to perform a rotational transformation of the inclined line into a vertical line, which is positioned at the same distance from the center as the shortest distance from the center to the inclined line. This transformation is shown in the following images.

Figure 168

Figure 169

In *Figure 168*, α is the angle between the perpendicular dropped from the line to the center of the coordinate system and the positive direction of the x -axis. In this case, the initial angle of the spiral is zero degrees ($k = 0$). In *Figure 169*, the inclined line is rotated so that the perpendicular to the center coincides with the positive x -axis, which rotates the initial angle of the spiral by 45 degrees clockwise. In this position, the situations in both images are identical. Their identity is defined by the equal angular distance between the perpendicular to the line's slope and the initial angle of the spiral - 45 degrees in this case. This means that the intersection points between the line and the spiral will be found at the same moments $t_{[n;m]}$ in both cases.

Before deriving the transformation formulas, we will use the already derived formulas to demonstrate that this is indeed the case.

Figure 170

Figure 171

In the images above, we can see that on the 15-th iteration of the third intersection point, the algorithm stops. In the annotations on the side, the initial values $nth_t: 3$ are completely identical in both cases. This represents the analytical part of the algorithm. In the iterative part $mth_t: 15$, we observe some discrepancies, but they occur beyond the chosen approximation accuracy of five decimal places. The difference beyond this point comes from the rounding errors in the calculations that the computer performs during the transformation. As we will see below, the transformation is quite complex and involves many operations, which contribute to this error. Nevertheless, the algorithm operates correctly within the chosen accuracy limits.

This was the geometric representation of the transformation. From an algebraic perspective, the transformation consists of incorporating the parameters a and b of the inclined line into the equation of the two-dimensional sequence. As we have shown, the transformation affects the initial angle of the spiral, expressed through the coefficient k , and the position of the vertical line x_l . Therefore, both values must be calculated as functions of the parameters k , a and b and substituted everywhere in the equation where they appear.

The transformed parameters k and x_l will be denoted as k' and x'_l , respectively. Substituting them into the KL -check equation, for example, will look as follows:

$$KL_{(k',x'_l)}^{[0V1]} = \left\lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{x'_l(k'-1)(k'-3)}{|E_{(x'_l(k'-1)(k'-3))}|}}{2} \right\rfloor. \quad (5.0.1)$$

Let's begin by deriving the equation for the transformed x_l .

Figure 168

We need to determine the length of the segment from the center of the coordinate system to the point x_l along with its sign. The sign is important for deriving k' as it determines in which quadrant the segment is located.

We will find them using the angle α and the length of the segment where the inclined line intersects the x -axis - this is the point $(0; \frac{-b}{a})$. In this case - $(0; 1)$.

The length of x_l is equal to the product of the cosine of the angle α and the length of the segment between the center and the intersection point of the line with the x -axis.

We find the angle α using the slope of the line a .

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|. \quad (5.0.2)$$

We take the absolute value of $\arctan(a)$ since we are only interested in the magnitude of the angle. The signs will be determined through algebraic checks.

For x'_l , we then have:

$$x'_l = \frac{-b}{E_{(a)}} \cos\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|\right). \quad (5.0.3)$$

We place the slope a into the eliminative function $E_{(a)}$ to avoid a division by zero error. Then, $x'_l = -b$. Here's how it looks:

Figure 172

The line has a slope of zero and a constant $b = 1$ instead of -1 . We will correct this with algebraic checks. The first check we will construct concerns the cases where the formula 5.0.3 is true. It is true when $a \neq 0$ and $b \neq 0$. We already have a check for b in the formula - this is the multiplier $\frac{-b}{E(a)}$. If $b = 0$, then $\frac{-b}{E(a)} = 0$.

Now, we will construct a switch that will check whether $a \neq 0$.

$$ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \frac{a}{E(a)}, \quad (5.0.4)$$

$$\overline{ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 1 - \frac{a}{E(a)}. \quad (5.0.5)$$

Here, we want this switch to return the expression $\frac{-b}{E(a)}\cos(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|)$ if $a \neq 0$ and the constant b when $a = 0$. Here's how it looks:

$$x'_l = \overline{ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]}}(b) + ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]} \left(\frac{-b}{E(a)}\cos(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|) \right). \quad (5.0.6)$$

The switch $ASwitch$ ensures the calculation of the correct value in magnitude and sign for x'_l in cases when $a = 0$. In the above figure, $b = 1$ and $x = 1$. Correctly calculating the sign of x'_l is critically important for the transformation k' , where this sign determines the direction in which the initial angle must be rotated using the coefficient k .

The formula covers all combinations of a and b . When both are zero, $x'_l = 0$. When the line is vertical, the slope is infinite, and then $\cos 0 \approx 1$ and $x'_l = \frac{-b}{E(a)} \approx 0$ if $|b| \ll |a|$.

In the image below, we see this case.

Figure 173

Now we move on to deriving the transformed coefficient k' .

The first problem we need to solve is finding the magnitude of the angle between the perpendicular to the inclined line and the x -axis. This is the angle by which we need to rotate the initial angle. We will determine its sign later.

The images below show four scenarios in which we take the angle between the perpendicular and the positive x -axis.

Figure 174

Figure 175

Figure 176

Figure 177

In all cases, the angle α as a function of the slope a is obtained by subtracting the absolute

value of the line's slope from 90 degrees.

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|. \quad (5.0.7)$$

Next, we need to convert this angle into a number. Let's call this number c .

$$c = \frac{\alpha}{\frac{\pi}{2}} = \frac{2(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|)}{\pi}. \quad (5.0.8)$$

The next problem is to determine what to do with this number - whether to add it to the initial angle, i.e., to the coefficient k , or to subtract it. We remind that the goal here is to reduce every possible case of an inclined line and a spiral to its equivalent case of a vertical line and a spiral.

If we examine the four images above, we will see that the most convenient approach is to rotate the initial angle of the spiral towards the nearest abscissa axis. For *Figures 174 and 175*, this is the positive abscissa, while for the other two, it is the negative abscissa. If the perpendicular of the slope is in the first and third quadrants (*Figures 174 and 177*), we should rotate the initial angle clockwise; in the other two quadrants (*Figures 175 and 176*), we rotate anticlockwise. The rotation direction depends on two factors - the signs of the constant b and the position of the line x_l . The correct signs will be obtained by defining an algebraic check - the Sign function. Let's call it *RCoeff* (*Rotational coefficient*), and pass as an argument the product of the two parameters with an inverse sign.

$$\text{RCoeff}_{(-bx_l)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}}. \quad (5.0.9)$$

Rotational Coefficient Table

	b	x_l	$-bx_l$
Fig. 174	1	1	-1
Fig. 175	1	-1	1
Fig. 176	1	-1	1
Fig. 177	-1	-1	-1

Figure 178

Now we can derive the formula for the transformed coefficient k' through rotation.

$$k' = k + \text{RCoeff}_{(-bx_l)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]}c, \quad (5.0.10)$$

$$k' = k + \frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}} \frac{2(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|)}{\pi}, \quad (5.0.11)$$

where k is the initial angular coefficient of the Archimedean spiral.

The definition domain of k' is different from the definition domain of k , because there are maximum and minimum values that can be added or subtracted from it. Since the formula for c deals with an angle of $\frac{\pi}{2}$, the maximum value that can be added is 1, and the minimum value is -1 . Then:

$$0 \leq k < 4, \quad (5.0.12)$$

$$0 - 1 \leq k' < 4 + 1, \quad (5.0.13)$$

$$-1 \leq k' < 5. \quad (5.0.14)$$

The last issue here concerns the boundary cases. We will examine them one by one. All other possibilities require a different approach, which, of course, involves the use of algebraic checks.

Case 1 - $a \neq 0, \quad b \neq 0$.

The formula 5.0.11 works for cases where both parameters a and b of the inclined line are non-zero.

To distinguish these cases, we will add a check to 5.0.11 that we already defined earlier (5.0.6) when deriving the formula for x'_l . This is the check *ASwitch*. We add it as a multiplier before the right-hand summand in 5.0.11.

$$k' = k + \text{ASwitch}_{(a)}^{[0 \vee 1]} \left(\frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}} \frac{2(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|)}{\pi} \right). \quad (5.0.15)$$

For the parameter b , we will not define a separate *BSwitch* check because this case is already covered by the coefficient *RCoeff*, which will return zero when $b = 0$. Instead, we will define only the opposite check *BSwitch*, which we will need shortly.

Case 2 - $a = 0, \quad b \neq 0$.

Let's return to the scenario from *Figure 172* which we used when defining x'_l .

Figure 172

Here we see that in order to become vertical, the horizontal line needs to be rotated by 90 degrees. The question is, however, which direction - whether in the positive or negative direction. Now, we will add the corresponding check to the equation for k' :

$$k' = k + \overline{ASwitch}_{(a)}^{[0V1]} + ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]} \left(\frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}} \frac{2(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|)}{\pi} \right). \quad (5.0.16)$$

When the slope $a = 0$, $\overline{ASwitch}$ will add 1 to the initial coefficient k of the spiral. Let's see what happens with the intersection points in this case.

Figure 179

Figure 180

As seen in both cases, when the signs of the constant b differ, the algorithm incorrectly positions the intersection points on the opposite side of the ordinate. This behavior arises from the formula for x'_l (5.0.6), which, when $a = 0$, has the following form:

$$x'_l = \overline{ASwitch}_{(a)}^{[0V1]}(b) = 1(b). \quad (5.0.17)$$

In this case, the formula for k' will correctly calculate the magnitude of the rotation angle, but not its direction. Let us check what the equivalent situations for the vertical line are in the two upper images.

Figure 181

Figure 182

In the case of a positive sign for b , comparing the moments $t_{[1;23]}$, we see that the algorithm actually calculates the wrong initial angle - instead of adding, it subtracts. In *Figure 180* $k = 0$, while in figure 181 $k = 3$ (which is equivalent to an initial angle with coefficient $k = -1$).

The situation is the same for a negative value of b .

Figure 183

Figure 184

The solution to this problem is to either change the sign of the constant b in the formula for x'_l , or change the sign of the check $ASwitch$ in the formula for k' . We will choose the second option.

$$k' = k - \overline{ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]}} + ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0\vee 1]} \left(\frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}} \frac{2\left(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)|\right)}{\pi} \right). \quad (5.0.18)$$

Let's check how this change works.

Figure 185

Figure 186

Figure 187

Figure 188

Case 3 - $a \neq 0, \quad b = 0$.

In this case, the inclined line passes through the center of the coordinate system.

Figure 189

To make the line vertical, we need to rotate it by an angle α to the ordinate axis.

$$\alpha = \frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan(a). \quad (5.0.19)$$

In this case, $\alpha = 90 - 33 = 57$ degrees and this situation corresponds to the case of a vertical line coinciding with the ordinate axis and the initial angle of the spiral 57 degrees.

Figure 190

In the two images below, we see that, in fact, the moments $t_{[2;0]}$ coincide for both spirals with an accuracy of up to the 7-th decimal place.

Figure 191

Figure 192

We add 5.0.19 to the formula for k' , but before that, let's define the corresponding algebraic check. As mentioned above, this is the check $\overline{BSwitch}$.

$$\overline{BSwitch}_{(b)}^{[0V1]} = 1 - \frac{b}{E_{(b)}}. \quad (5.0.20)$$

Thus, the formula for k' takes the form:

$$k' = k - \overline{ASwitch}_{(a)}^{[0V1]} + ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]} \left(\frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}} \cdot \frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)| \right)}{\pi} \right) + \overline{BSwitch}_{(b)}^{[0V1]} \left(\frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan(a) \right)}{\pi} \right), \quad (5.0.21)$$

where we have accounted for the fact that the expression in parentheses $\frac{2(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan(a))}{\pi}$ transforms the angle into a coefficient.

Let's examine the final case.

Case 4 - $a = 0$, $b = 0$.

This is the scenario where the inclined line coincides with the x -axis. Here, the solution is the easiest because, to be transformed into a vertical line, the horizontal line needs to be rotated by 90 degrees. A right angle corresponds to an angular coefficient of 1. The direction of rotation does not matter. The images below directly illustrate the equivalence between the horizontal line at $k = 0$ and the vertical line at $k = 1$.

Figure 193

Figure 194

Let's still demonstrate that the direction of rotation of the initial angle does not matter. The image below shows the same moment $t_{[1;0]}$ for a vertical line with an initial angular

coefficient $k = 3$.

Figure 195

Since the sign does not matter, we will choose the plus sign, i.e., when $a = 0$ and $b = 0$, we add 1 to the initial coefficient k . This can be easily achieved by multiplying the corresponding checks $ASwitch$ and $BSwitch$, which return 1 in this scenario. Then, the equation for k' takes the form:

$$k' = k - \overline{ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]}} + ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]} \left(\frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}} \cdot \frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)| \right)}{\pi} \right) + \overline{BSwitch_{(b)}^{[0V1]}} \left(\frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan(a) \right)}{\pi} \right) + \left(\overline{ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]}} \right) \left(\overline{BSwitch_{(b)}^{[0V1]}} \right). \quad (5.0.22)$$

The reason the equation correctly adds the value 1 is complex and not only due to the product of the two checks. The key factor here is the fourth term. Let's substitute the values $a = b = 0$ and verify.

$$k' = k - 1 + 0 \left(\frac{-0x_l}{E_{(-0x_l)}} \frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - 0 \right)}{\pi} \right) + 1 \left(\frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - 0 \right)}{\pi} \right) + 1.1, \quad (5.0.23)$$

$$k' = k + 1. \quad (5.0.24)$$

This was the last problem in our discussion. Let's present the formulas for rotational transformation together, which allow the solution for the intersection points between a line and a spiral to be generalized for an inclined line as well.

Formula for the position of the equivalent vertical line:

$$x'_l = \overline{ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]}} (b) + ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]} \left(\frac{-b}{E_{(a)}} \cos \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)| \right) \right). \quad (5.06)$$

Formula for the equivalent coefficient of the initial angle of the spiral:

$$k' = k - \overline{ASwitch}_{(a)}^{[0V1]} + ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]} \left(\frac{-bx_l}{E_{(-bx_l)}} \cdot \frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - |\arctan(a)| \right)}{\pi} \right) + \overline{BSwitch}_{(b)}^{[0V1]} \left(\frac{2 \left(\frac{\pi}{2} - \arctan(a) \right)}{\pi} \right) + \left(ASwitch_{(a)}^{[0V1]} \right) \left(BSwitch_{(b)}^{[0V1]} \right). \quad (5.0.22)$$

Finally, we will show several situations with an inclined and a vertical line and their representation in a t-diagram.

Figure 196

Figure 197

Figure 198

Figure 199

Figure 200

Figure 201

Figure 202

Figure 203

6 Appendix 1 - Sequences with arbitrary terms and parametric spirals of an infinite order

6.1 Sequences with arbitrary terms

The statement $0^0 = 1$ can also be used for the algebraic construction of numerical sequences with arbitrary terms. By definition, a numerical sequence (or simply a sequence) is an ordered set of elements, where each element is associated with a natural number n through a function, and is obtained as its value. Each term of the sequence is obtained from n by some rule. For example, the sequence with the general term a_n :

$$\{a_n\} = n^2. \quad (6.1.1)$$

The rule defines the values of the sequence based on the position number of each term. Now we will define a sequence where each term is associated with a natural number, but the values of the terms are not a function of the position number.

$$\{a_n\} = 0^{|n-1|}x_1 + 0^{|n-2|}x_2 + 0^{|n-3|}x_3 \dots 0^{|n-k|}x_k, \quad n, k \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (6.1.2)$$

We define the numerical sequence $\{a_n\}$ as a sum of variables x_k with coefficients $0^{|n-k|}$. This sum nullifies all the terms of the sequence except for the chosen n -th term. For example, for $n = 2$, we have:

$$a_2 = 0x_1 + 1x_2 + 0x_3 \dots 0x_k = x_2. \quad (6.1.3)$$

It is clear that the variables x_k are the arbitrary elements of the sequence. They can be replaced with a number, a function, another sequence, another term of the same sequence (i.e., recursion), etc. Here is an example:

$$\{a_{n,x}\} = 0^{|n-1|}5 + 0^{|n-2|}x^2 + 0^{|n-3|}\sqrt{x} + 0^{|n-4|}\sin x + 0^{|n-5|}e^x + 0^{|n-6|}(a_{2,3} + a_{3,x^2}). \quad (6.1.4)$$

We add x as an argument along with the index n since it appears in several of the terms of the sequence. Let us consider some of them.

$$a_{2,3} = 3^2 = 9; \quad a_{5,3} = e^3; \quad a_{5,e} = e^e; \quad a_{6,2} = 4 + 2 = 6. \quad (6.1.5)$$

Adding the variable x provides another level of flexibility in the sequence because the same term in the sequence has different values depending on x . In any arbitrary sequence, a

given term can represent a whole series of mathematical operations, which can include both independent expressions and terms from the sequence itself. In the example above, this is the sixth term of the sequence. The formula derived in the main exposition for the two-dimensional numerical sequence is actually an arbitrary numerical sequence whose terms are separate algorithms. It is clear that algebraic checks can also be added before each term of the sequence, as we did for the two-dimensional sequence.

The numerical sequence defined in this way with arbitrary terms is, in fact, an algebraic analog of an array in programming languages. We have seen how this algebraic structure can be used to construct complex algorithms. In the next section, we will demonstrate another possible application of it – avoiding complex actions such as taking successive derivatives and integrals.

6.2 Parametric spirals of an infinite order

In this section, we will explore the possibility of defining a separate class of spirals based on t-parameterization. Their number is literally infinite, and some of them have truly peculiar shapes.

Let's begin with the formulas for the x and y components of a parameterized Archimedean spiral.

$$x(t) = vt\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), \quad (6.2.1)$$

$$y(t) = vt\sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), \quad (6.2.2)$$

$v \in \mathbb{R}, v \geq 0$ - radial velocity,

$\omega \in \mathbb{R}$ - angular velocity,

$0 \leq k < 4$ - initial angular coefficient.

In section *4.2 Derivatives of an Archimedean Spiral*, we have already defined the first derivatives of $x(t)$ and $y(t)$.

$$x'(t) = v \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right), \quad (6.2.3)$$

$$y'(t) = v \left(\sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + \omega t \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right). \quad (6.2.4)$$

Seen on their own, these are simply two equations, even though they were obtained through differentiation from two other equations. Nothing prevents us from visualizing them as well.

Figure 204

On the display on the second row to the left under *Spiral parameters*;, we have *deg*: [1, 1]. This shows the degree of the derivative of the Archimedean spiral in the format: [*x-derivative*, *y-derivative*].

In this specific case, these are the first derivatives. The spiral constructed through them closely resembles the Archimedean spiral, with the difference being that its expansion does not start from the center of the coordinate system (0,0), but from (0.5, 0). The starting point on the *x*-coordinate is set by the radial velocity *v*. Let's see what this spiral looks like in the *t*-diagram.

Figure 205

Let's zoom in on the image in the area around the center of the coordinate system.

Figure 206

The green line traces the increase of the radius vector of the spiral, and we can see that near the center, it forms a curved line.

The process of differentiation can continue indefinitely since the formulas contain trigonometric functions. Let's focus only on the x -coordinate and take the next three derivatives.

$$x''(t) = v\omega \left(-2\sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right), \quad (6.2.5)$$

$$x'''(t) = v\omega^2 \left(-3\cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) + \omega t \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right), \quad (6.2.6)$$

$$x''''(t) = v\omega^3 \left(4\sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) + \omega t \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.7)$$

A clear pattern for the n -th derivative emerges:

$$\frac{d^n x}{dt^n} = v\omega^{n-1} \left(n \frac{d^{n-1}}{dt^{n-1}} \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \frac{d^{n-1}}{dt^{n-1}} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.8)$$

However, there is a problem with this formula – substituting n with a given value will lead to an incorrect result. The reason for this is the chain rule of differentiation. Let's choose $n = 2$ and perform the operations in the formula step by step.

$$\frac{d^2 x}{dt^2} = v\omega^1 \left(2 \frac{d}{dt} \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \frac{d}{dt} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.9)$$

We substituted $n = 2$ and see that we need to take the first derivatives of the trigonometric functions. They are as follows:

$$\frac{d}{dt} \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) = -\omega \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right), \quad (6.2.10)$$

$$\frac{d}{dt} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) = \omega \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right). \quad (6.2.11)$$

We substitute in 6.2.9:

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = v\omega^1 \left(-2\omega \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega^2 t \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right), \quad (6.2.12)$$

$$\frac{d^2x}{dt^2} = v\omega^2 \left(-2\sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.13)$$

Comparing this result with 6.2.5, we see that the expression inside the parentheses is the same, but outside the parentheses, we have ω^2 instead of ω . The chain rule introduces a factor of ω outside the parentheses, and the exponent of this factor will grow along with n , as it directly depends on the number of times we differentiate inside the parentheses.

There are two ways to address this issue. One is simply to remove ω from equation 6.2.8, and then we will have:

$$\frac{d^n x}{dt^n} = v \left(n \frac{d^{n-1}}{dt^{n-1}} \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \frac{d^{n-1}}{dt^{n-1}} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.14)$$

This solution is valid, but it does not suit us because it does not save us from performing differentiation $(n - 1)$ times inside the parentheses.

Things get even worse with successive integration - as we will see below - because it will require integration by parts the corresponding number of times. However, there is a way to bypass these operations so that the $(n - 1)$ -th derivative (or integral) can be obtained solely based on n by substitution into the new formula.

Here, the defined numerical sequence with arbitrary values comes into play.

We will use the fact that the derivatives of trigonometric functions are cyclic. We define a sequence of four terms representing the order of trigonometric derivatives.

$$\{D_n\} = 0^{|n|} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) + 0^{|n-1|} \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - 0^{|n-2|} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - 0^{|n-3|} \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right). \quad (6.2.15)$$

We define this sequence for indices from 0 to 3 so that we can access them using modular division by 4. The definition set of the indices n should be defined as $n \in \mathbb{Z}$ because the logic of sequential differentiation and integration allows for this, thereby providing a greater variety of parametric spirals.

The cycle of derivatives of the sine function consists of only four steps. This means that the index n must be reduced to just four numbers. The most convenient way to achieve this is through modular division, which, however, will reduce n to zero for every n that is a multiple of 4.

Let us first substitute the derivatives of the trigonometric functions in 6.2.8 with the appropriate term from the sequence D_n .

$$\frac{d^n x}{dt^n} = v\omega^{n-1} (nD_n - \omega t D_{n-1}). \quad (6.2.16)$$

Now we need to verify whether we are correctly substituting the trigonometric functions. For the first derivative $n = 1$, the equation for the x -component has the form:

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = v \left(\cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.17)$$

Indeed:

$$D_1 = \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right), \quad (6.2.18)$$

$$D_0 = \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right). \quad (6.2.19)$$

The general formula for each n , including the modular division in the indices of the numerical sequence, is as follows:

$$\frac{d^n x}{dt^n} = v\omega^{n-1} \left(nD_{(n)\bmod 4} - \omega t D_{(n-1)\bmod 4} \right). \quad (6.2.20)$$

Let's check for $n > 4$, for example, $n = 6$.

$$\frac{d^6 x}{dt^6} = v\omega^5 \left(-6\sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right), \quad (6.2.21)$$

$$D_{(6)\bmod 4} = D_2 = -\sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right), \quad (6.2.22)$$

$$D_{(5)\bmod 4} = D_1 = \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right). \quad (6.2.23)$$

Before we check how things stand for $n \leq 0$, where we need to integrate instead of differentiating, let's first look at the corresponding formulas for the y -component of the parameterized spiral.

$$y(t) = v t \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right), \quad (6.2.24)$$

$$y'(t) = v \left(\sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) + \omega t \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right), \quad (6.2.25)$$

$$y''(t) = v\omega \left(2\cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right), \quad (6.2.26)$$

$$y'''(t) = v\omega^2 \left(-3\sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) - \omega t \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right), \quad (6.2.27)$$

$$y''''(t) = v\omega^3 \left(-4\cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) + \omega t \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.28)$$

The model is similar to $\frac{d^n x}{dt^n}$ but with swapped trigonometric functions and signs.

$$\frac{d^n y}{dt^n} = v\omega^{n-1} \left(n \frac{d^{n-1}}{dt^{n-1}} \sin\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) + \omega t \frac{d^{n-1}}{dt^{n-1}} \cos\left(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t\right) \right). \quad (6.2.29)$$

The corresponding formula with the numerical sequence $\{D_n\}$ is as follows:

$$\frac{d^n y}{dt^n} = v\omega^{n-1} \left(nD_{(n-1)\bmod 4} + \omega t D_{(n)\bmod 4} \right). \quad (6.2.30)$$

This sequence of derivatives allows us to define an infinite number of variations of parametric spirals. To denote them, we can adopt the following notation:

$$S_{(t)}^{n,m} : \mathbb{R} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^2, \quad S_{(t)}^{n,m} = \left(\frac{d^n x}{dt^n}, \frac{d^m y}{dt^m} \right), \quad n, m \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (6.2.31)$$

$$S_{(t)}^{n,m} = \left(v\omega^{n-1} (nD_{(n)\bmod 4} - \omega t D_{(n-1)\bmod 4}), v\omega^{n-1} (mD_{(m-1)\bmod 4} + \omega t D_{(m)\bmod 4}), \right) \quad (6.2.32)$$

where n is the order of the derivative of the x -component, and m is the order of the derivative of the y -component of the parametric spiral S . In this notation, the Archimedean spiral will look like this:

$$S_{(t)}^{0,0} = \left(v t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), v t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right). \quad (6.2.33)$$

From the perspective of this formula, the Archimedean spiral is a parametric spiral of zero degree ($n = 0, m = 0$), or more briefly, a *zero parametric spiral*.

Now let's consider the cases where $n \leq 0$. We will start with $n = 0$. Substituting into 6.2.8 for the x -component we obtain:

$$\frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} = v\omega^{-1} \left(0 \frac{d^{-1}}{dt^{-1}} \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t \frac{d^{-1}}{dt^{-1}} \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right), \quad (6.2.34)$$

$$\frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} = -v\omega t \frac{d^{-1}}{dt^{-1}} \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t). \quad (6.2.35)$$

The first problem - the presence of ω as a factor - has already been resolved using the numerical sequence with arbitrary values. The second problem is the negative derivative. From the fundamental theorem of calculus, it follows that the negative first derivative is equivalent to the first antiderivative. Let's integrate 6.2.8 for $n = 1$ to see what happens.

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = v \left(\cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right), \quad (6.2.36)$$

$$\int \frac{dx}{dt} dt = \int v \left(\cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right) dt, \quad (6.2.37)$$

$$\int \frac{dx}{dt} dt = \int v \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) dt - \int v \omega t \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) dt, \quad (6.2.38)$$

$$\int \frac{dx}{dt} dt = \frac{v}{\omega} \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + C_1 - \left(-v t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + \frac{v}{\omega} \sin(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + C_2 \right), \quad (6.2.39)$$

$$\int \frac{dx}{dt} dt = v t \cos(k \frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + C_1 + C_2. \quad (6.2.40)$$

As expected, we obtain the formula for the x -component of the Archimedean spiral if we set $C_1 = C_2 = 0$. We remind that we have just computed the integral of the first derivative of the x -component. Now, we will compare the obtained result with the formula 6.2.20 using the numerical sequence:

$$\frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} = v\omega^{-1} (0D_{(0)\bmod 4} - \omega t D_{(-1)\bmod 4}), \quad (6.2.41)$$

$$\frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} = v\omega^{-1} (0D_0 - \omega t D_3), \quad (6.2.42)$$

$$\frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} = v\omega^{-1} \left(0 \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) - \omega t (-\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t)) \right), \quad (6.2.43)$$

$$\frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} = v t \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t). \quad (6.2.44)$$

We see that the modular division in the indices of the sequence selects the correct term. This formula also has the advantage of not computing integration constants, despite yielding the same result as standard integration.

Let's finally check for $n < 0$. Let's integrate 6.2.43.

$$\int \frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} dt = \int v t \cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) dt, \quad (6.2.45)$$

$$\int \frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} dt = \frac{v}{\omega^2} \left(\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) + \omega t \sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t) \right) + C_1 + C_2. \quad (6.2.46)$$

We compare with the formula for the x -th derivative.

$$\frac{d^{-1} x}{dt^{-1}} = v\omega^{-2} (-1D_{(-1)\bmod 4} - \omega t D_{(-1-1)\bmod 4}), \quad (6.2.47)$$

$$\frac{d^{-1} x}{dt^{-1}} = v\omega^{-2} (-1D_3 - \omega t D_2), \quad (6.2.48)$$

$$D_3 = -\cos(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t), \quad (6.2.49)$$

$$D_2 = -\sin(k\frac{\pi}{2} + \omega t). \quad (6.2.50)$$

Again, if we assume $C_1 = C_2 = 0$, then:

$$\int \frac{d^0 x}{dt^0} dt = v\omega^{-2} (-1D_3 - \omega t D_2), \quad (6.2.51)$$

or more general:

$$\int \frac{d^n x}{dt^n} dt = v\omega^{n-2} ((n-1)D_{(n-1)\bmod 4} - \omega t D_{(n-2)\bmod 4}), \quad (6.2.52)$$

$$\int \frac{d^m y}{dt^m} dt = v\omega^{m-2} ((m-1)D_{(m-2)\bmod 4} + \omega t D_{(m-1)\bmod 4}). \quad (6.2.53)$$

Now let's discuss why we can eliminate integration constants when integrating. As we have seen, the cyclic nature of the derivatives of the sine function allows the differentiation process to continue indefinitely. The same applies in the opposite direction with integration.

This means that any given link n in this infinite chain can be obtained in two ways - either by differentiating $n - 1$, or by integrating from $n + 1$. It depends on where we start in order to reach n . However, the formula for the n -th derivative with an arbitrary numerical sequence allows this derivative to be found directly by substitution, instead of through the tedious and often quite cumbersome process of differentiation or integration.

Indeed, if we decide to define the spiral $S_{(t)}^{-11,-11}$, starting from $S_{(t)}^{0,0}$, we would need to perform integration by parts twenty two times.

Let's still examine the role of the integration constant in parameterized spirals. We will integrate both components of the spiral $S_{(t)}^{1,1}$ and obtain the Archimedean spiral $S_{(t)}^{0,0}$. Let $C_1 + C_2 = 1$ for both components.

Figure 207

As seen, the integration constant shifts the starting point of the spiral to the point (1, 1). Since the primary goal of the formula for parameterized spirals is to define curves, we can assume that we define them centered at the origin of the coordinate system. Therefore, we can disregard the integration constant by setting it to zero.

Now that we have derived the general formula for the parameterized spiral, let's see how they look. First, we note that there is nothing that requires $n = m$, i.e., the degrees of the derivatives of the spiral components to be equal. When $n = m$, the spirals closely resemble the Archimedean spiral. Above, we have shown $S_{(t)}^{1,1}$. The unusual-looking spirals appear when $n \neq m$. Here are a few examples. We will display the spirals in both modes - in the Cartesian coordinate system and in the t-diagram.

Figure 208

Figure 209

Here we have an ellipsoidal spiral $S_{(t)}^{0,2}$, whose minor and major axes are oriented along the abscissa and ordinate, respectively. In the t-diagram, it is very evident that the magnitude of the radius vector varies sinusoidally, despite the radial velocity being constant.

Figure 210

Figure 211

$S_{(t)}^{3,1}$ is also an ellipsoidal spiral, but with the opposite axis orientation compared to the previous spiral.

As we mentioned, when $n = m$, the spiral closely resembles the Archimedean spiral. Such is also $S_{(t)}^{2,2}$.

Figure 212

Figure 213

The next spiral $S_{(t)}^{-2,0}$ has a negative derivative for the x -coordinate, a less pronounced ellipsoidal shape with its major axis oriented at 45 degrees, and its radius vector also "jumps," but less noticeably than in the previous spirals with different orders.

Figure 214

Figure 215

For the next spiral, we will integrate the x -component once more and observe an even stranger shape. The spiral $S_{(t)}^{-3,0}$ appears to have focal points along the minor axis and an inclination of approximately 135 degrees.

Figure 216

Figure 217

Let's also show a spiral with equal negative exponents.

Figure 218

Figure 219

Let us stop here with the demonstrations of spirals. The present exposition does not aim at an extensive study of them. In general, we can say that when the component exponents are equal, the spirals resemble the Archimedean spiral. When they are different, the spirals exhibit a more or less pronounced ellipsoidal shape with varying orientation relative to the coordinate axes.

Finally, we will show that the solution for intersection points between an Archimedean spiral and a straight line applies only to the Archimedean spiral.

Figure 220

The likely reason (or at least one of the reasons) for the non-applicability of the algorithm for intersection points is the variable length of the radius vector. As we saw in the t-diagrams of the spirals shown above, the radius vector does not grow at the same rate, even though the radial velocity in all the parametric spiral equations is constant. Finding a general solution for intersection points between a straight line and a parametric spiral of arbitrary order remains the subject of further research. Also, the question of intersection points between a parametric spiral (in particular, an Archimedean spiral) and a curved line — such as a parabola, hyperbola, sinusoid, etc. — remains open for now.

7 Appendix 2 - Eliminative function extension

In the first section of the main exposition, we defined an eliminative function whose role is to algebraically eliminate the value 0 for the variable x belonging to the set of real numbers. Let us recall the formula.

$$E_{(x)}^{[1 \vee x]} = x^{1-0^{|x|}}, \quad (1.3.23)$$

$$E_{(x)}^{[1 \vee x]} = x, \quad x \neq 0, \quad (1.3.24)$$

$$E_{(x)}^{[1 \vee x]} = 1, \quad x = 0. \quad (1.3.25)$$

When the variable takes the value 0, the eliminative function changes this value and assigns another value to the variable instead, in this case, 1. Now, we will show that the formula can be extended for an arbitrary value of the variable to be replaced. We have already done this in the section on numerical sequences with arbitrary values, where we defined coefficients $0^{|n-k|}$ for each distinct variable x_k of the sequence.

$$\{a_n\} = 0^{|n-1|}x_1 + 0^{|n-2|}x_2 + 0^{|n-3|}x_3 \dots 0^{|n-k|}x_k, \quad n, k \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (6.1.2)$$

The extension of the eliminative function is performed in the exponent of the eliminative function's formula. Then we have:

$$E_{(x,a)}^{[1\vee x]} = x^{1-0^{|a-x|}}, \quad x, a \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (7.0.1)$$

$$E_{(x,a)}^{[1\vee x]} = x, \quad x \neq a, \quad (7.0.2)$$

$$E_{(x,a)}^{[1\vee x]} = 1, \quad x = a. \quad (7.0.3)$$

This value substitution can be observed if we display the variable x on the number line. For the standard eliminative function, this would look as follows:

As we can see, instead of the number 0, we have another number - the number 1. In other words, on this number line, there is no zero; instead, there are two ones. There is no algebraic meaning to this. One of the real meanings of numbers is that they are an abstract idea of distance. When this abstract idea is embodied in a number line, then each number represents the distance between it and the center of the line - the number 0. The signs of the numbers indicate on which side of zero the corresponding number lies - positive on the right, negative on the left. However, as distances from zero, they are equivalent, and algebraically this is expressed by the modulus of the number. Placing a number other than zero at the center of the number line has no real meaning - the number 0 is the only number without length, i.e., it is a point. All other numbers are also points in themselves, just like 0, but they receive additional meaning that comes from their distance and position relative to it. The number 2 is at a distance of 2 units to the right of zero, and the number -2 is 2 units to the left of it. In this sense, numbers are names of distances relative to a chosen point. So, if we look at numbers from a semantic point of view, they are exactly that - *names* of points relative to another point. The number 0 is also a name, but for a point with a special status - the status of a center, from which all other points get their names. From this perspective, on the number line shown above, the number 0 is missing. More precisely, the name *zero* is missing, and in its place, we have another name - the name *one*. If we look at it realistically, though, the length of the number 2, for example, is still 2, measured from the central point, whose name in this case is *one*.

Let's now demonstrate the replacement of another value from the number line using the extended eliminative function. Let's choose $a = -4$.

What we are doing here is giving the name *one* to a point on the number line that is located four units to the left of the central point 0. In reality, we are changing the semantics of the numbers in a perfectly valid and mathematically accepted way, using the basic assumption for the expression $0^0 = 1$.

Now we will define another extension of the eliminative function, which will allow us to name any point on the number line arbitrarily. This extension is based on the fact that

the eliminative function returns the number 1 at the chosen value a . This allows us to introduce the chosen name, which is a real number, by adding a multiplier in front of it. Let's denote the arbitrary number by b . The requirement is that in all cases where the argument $x \neq a$ is passed, the eliminative function should return the argument x itself; in the case when $x = a$, the eliminative function should return b . Here, a switch can again be used. Here's how we extend the eliminative function to achieve this. Let's call this extended eliminative function the *replacement function* and denote it by R .

$$R_{(x,a,b)}^{[b\vee x]} = b^{0^{|a-x|}} E_{(x,a)}^{[1\vee x]}, \quad x, a, b \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (7.0.4)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b)}^{[b\vee x]} = b^{0^{|a-x|}} x^{1-0^{|a-x|}}, \quad x, a, b \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (7.0.5)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b)}^{[b\vee x]} = x, \quad x \neq a, \quad (7.0.6)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b)}^{[b\vee x]} = b, \quad x = a. \quad (7.0.7)$$

It is clear that the multiplier b can also be replaced with a function or another mathematical expression. Let $b = \cos\frac{\pi}{3}$ and $a = 1$.

We can replace more than one value with more than one arbitrary value.

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee x]} = d^{0^{|c-x|}} b^{0^{|a-x|}} x^{1-0^{(|a-x|)(|c-x|)}}, \quad x, a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (7.0.8)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee x]} = x, \quad x \neq a, \quad x \neq c, \quad (7.0.9)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee x]} = b, \quad x = a, \quad (7.0.10)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee x]} = d, \quad x = c. \quad (7.0.11)$$

Let's display a number line with two replaced values. We will replace the number 5 with -43 and 0 with 29.

The replacement function has semantic similarities with dictionaries in programming languages. A dictionary is a data structure in which a specific value, called a *key*, is mapped to another value, called a *value*. The keys are unique, while the assigned values may be identical. In the replacement function, a continuous variable is both a key and a value for each of its values, allowing us to assign any value to any key. In the formula above, we have the keys a and c , which are assigned the values b and d , respectively.

According to the scheme from formula 7.0.8, an infinite number of keys can be added to the replacement function. As we can see, the keys are added as factors $(k - x)$ in the exponents, while the values are added as factors in front of the extended eliminative function.

We can do various things with the replacement function. We can remove the eliminative function and keep only the keys a and c along with their values b and d . For all other values of the variable x , the function will return 1.

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee 1]} = d^{0|c-x|} b^{0|a-x|}, \quad x, a, b, c, d \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (7.0.12)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x \neq a, \quad x \neq c, \quad (7.0.13)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee 1]} = b, \quad x = a, \quad (7.0.14)$$

$$R_{(x,a,b,c,d)}^{[b\vee d\vee 1]} = d, \quad x = c. \quad (7.0.15)$$

In this case, the replacement function cannot be considered a dictionary since it contains an infinite number of identical keys - the number 1.

It is entirely possible, instead of assigning single values to a given key, to assign multiple values. We can assign a numerical sequence. Let us take the already defined arbitrary sequence of 6.1.2.

$$R_{(x,c,n)}^{[a_n \vee x]} = a_n^{0|c-x|} x^{1-0|c-x|}, \quad x, c \in \mathbb{R}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}, \quad (7.0.16)$$

$$R_{(x,c,n)}^{[a_n \vee x]} = x \quad x \neq c, \quad (7.0.17)$$

$$R_{(x,c,n)}^{[a_n \vee x]} = a_n \quad x = c, \quad (7.0.18)$$

where a_n is the n -th term of the sequence $\{a_n\}$. If we substitute the algebraic expression for $\{a_n\}$ in the replacement function, we will have:

$$R_{(x,c,n)}^{[a_n \vee x]} = (0^{|n-1|}x_1 + 0^{|n-2|}x_2 + 0^{|n-3|}x_3 \dots 0^{|n-k|}x_k)^{0|c-x|} x^{1-0|c-x|}, \quad x, c \in \mathbb{R}, \quad n \in \mathbb{N}. \quad (7.0.19)$$

This is analogous to the common practice in programming where an array is assigned as a value to a key in a dictionary.

Besides changing specific values, we can also modify values within a given interval. For example, we can change the signs of the variable within this interval. We will do this using the sign function. Let's recall it.

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{x}{|E_{(x)}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (7.0.20)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > 0, \quad (7.0.21)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = -1, \quad x < 0, \quad (7.0.22)$$

$$S_{(x)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x = 0. \quad (7.0.23)$$

First, we will extend the sign function itself.

$$S_{(x,a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = \frac{x - a}{|E_{(x-a)}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (7.0.24)$$

$$S_{(x,a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > a, \quad (7.0.25)$$

$$S_{(x,a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = -1, \quad x < a, \quad (7.0.26)$$

$$S_{(x,a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x = a. \quad (7.0.27)$$

With this extension, the sign function can shift the position of the zero boundary between positive and negative numbers. The change of location, in turn, can be used to control the signs of the variable. To demonstrate this, we will introduce another modification to the function. Let us call this function CS - the sign change function.

$$CS_{(x,a)} = |x| S_{(x,a)}^{[-1\vee 0\vee 1]} = |x| \frac{x - a}{|E_{(x-a)}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (7.0.28)$$

By multiplying the absolute value of the variable x by its sign, we will be able to see a new number line. Let us see how the variable x looks for $a = 3$.

The function CS not only replaces the number 3 with 0 but also places negative signs between the two zeros.

Obviously, for $a = 0$, we have the variable x itself.

Now we can define a change in the values of the variable within a specific interval.

$$CS_{(x,a,b)} = |x| \frac{(x - a)(x - b)}{|E_{((x-a)(x-b))}^{[1\vee x]}|}. \quad (7.0.29)$$

Let us choose $a = -3$ and $b = 3$.

Here we have an axis with three zeros and negative numbers between the two outer zeros on the left and right, while positive numbers occupy the remaining part of the domain of x .

The change of signs of the variable can be used to control a given function without modifying the expression of the function itself. In the image below, we have the function $y(x) = x$. Instead of the argument x , we pass the function $\text{CS}_{(x,a,b)}$ with arguments $a = 1$ and $b = 4$. To obtain the straight line of the function, we will replace the absolute value of x from 7.0.29 with the argument x itself.

$$\text{CS}_{(x,a,b)} = x \frac{(x-a)(x-b)}{|E_{((x-a)(x-b))}^{[1 \vee x]}|} \quad (7.0.30)$$

Figure 221

We see that the behavior of the function is the same as its standard behavior, with the difference that in the interval $x \in [1, 4]$, its value is the same as in the interval $x \in [-4, -1]$ but with opposite sign. This substitution of the argument makes the continuous function $y(x)=x$ discontinuous at the points $x = 1$ and $x = 4$. If we represent the variable x defined in this way on the number line, we will see that in the chosen interval, the numbers are negative, and at the positions of 1 and 4, we have 0.

Let's see how the function $y(x) = \sin x$ looks in the same interval with the argument x modified by the function CS.

Figure 222

Again, we see that the function values remain the same as in the interval $x \in [-4, -1]$, but instead of an inverted slope, we have a phase inversion.

Something interesting happens with the function $y(x) = \sqrt{x}$. Let's take a look.

Figure 223

In the given interval, the function has no values because the sign of the argument in this interval is negative.

For negative values of the variable, however, the function is defined because, as we showed on the number line above, the function CS reverses the signs, making the values positive.

Here we have defined values of the function for a negative argument because CS converts the argument into a positive one. We will stop with the demonstrations of functions

modified through their arguments, as an extensive study of this problem goes beyond the scope of the current exposition.

8 Appendix 3 - Prime numbers and algebraic checks

In this section, we will briefly discuss several possible applications of algebraic checks in relation to problems involving prime numbers. We will derive a check to determine whether a given natural number n is prime or not, and based on this check, we will derive formulas for counting prime numbers up to a given number N , as well as formulas for the factorials of prime and composite numbers.

Let us begin with an algebraic check to determine whether a given natural number n is prime. At the beginning of the main exposition, we defined the reduction function $B_{(x)}^{[0V1]}$.

$$B_{(x)}^{[0V1]} = \lceil x \rceil - \lfloor x \rfloor, \quad x \in \mathbb{R}, \quad (1.3.2)$$

$$B_{(x)}^{[0V1]} = 0, \quad x \in \mathbb{Z}, \quad (1.3.3)$$

$$B_{(x)}^{[0V1]} = 1, \quad x \notin \mathbb{Z}. \quad (1.3.4)$$

If the argument x is a non-integer, $B_{(x)}^{[0V1]}$ returns 1; if it is an integer, it returns 0. This function is very useful for checking whether a given natural number is prime, as the question of whether a number is prime or not essentially concerns its divisibility. Prime numbers are those that are not exactly divisible by any number other than 1 and themselves, while composite numbers are those that, in addition to being divisible by 1 and themselves, are also divisible by at least one other number.

The verification process involves iterating through all natural numbers greater than 1 and smaller than the given number, checking for divisibility. We define the algebraic check *IsPrime* as the product of the results from each individual iteration.

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0V1]} = \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} B_{(\frac{n}{k})}^{[0V1]}, \quad n \geq 3, \quad (8.0.1)$$

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0V1]} = \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} (\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor), \quad n \geq 3. \quad (8.0.2)$$

For the upper limit of the product, we set the number $\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil$, because there is no need to check divisibility for numbers greater than the square root of the given number n . For example, for all numbers up to and including 9, it is sufficient to check divisibility only by 2 and 3.

We apply the ceiling function to the square root because the upper limit must be an integer. The iteration process should start from the first odd prime number, 3. If we start from 2, then:

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(2)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} B_{\binom{n}{k}}^{[0\vee 1]} = (\lceil \frac{2}{2} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{2}{2} \rfloor) = 0, \quad (8.0.3)$$

which is obviously an incorrect result. But for $n = 3$:

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(3)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} B_{\binom{n}{k}}^{[0\vee 1]} = (\lceil \frac{3}{2} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{3}{2} \rfloor) = 1, \quad (8.0.4)$$

Let us now examine how the *IsPrime*-check works by constructing the corresponding products for $n = 5$, $n = 6$ and $n = 7$.

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(5)}^{[0\vee 1]} = (\lceil \frac{5}{2} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{5}{2} \rfloor)(\lceil \frac{5}{3} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{5}{3} \rfloor) = 1.1 = 1, \quad (8.0.5)$$

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(6)}^{[0\vee 1]} = (\lceil \frac{6}{2} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{6}{2} \rfloor)(\lceil \frac{6}{3} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{6}{3} \rfloor) = 0.0 = 0, \quad (8.0.6)$$

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(7)}^{[0\vee 1]} = (\lceil \frac{7}{2} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{7}{2} \rfloor)(\lceil \frac{7}{3} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{7}{3} \rfloor) = 1.1 = 1. \quad (8.0.7)$$

Let us also examine $n = 10$. Then the upper limit $\lceil \sqrt{10} \rceil = 4$.

$$\text{IsPrime}_{(10)}^{[0\vee 1]} = (\lceil \frac{10}{2} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{10}{2} \rfloor)(\lceil \frac{10}{3} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{10}{3} \rfloor)(\lceil \frac{10}{4} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{10}{4} \rfloor) = 0.1.1 = 0. \quad (8.0.8)$$

As we can see, it is sufficient for the product to contain just one zero (i.e., the number being searched is divisible by some number without remainder at least once) and the algebraic check returns the answer "not a prime number".

Now we can proceed to constructing algorithms for the factorials of prime and composite numbers up to a given number n , as well as for the factorials of the first n prime and composite numbers. These are two different types of factorials, as we will see.

Constructing the factorial of prime numbers up to a given n is based on the *IsPrime* check, where we will raise the given number n to the power of the check itself. Then, if the number n is prime, we will have:

$$n^{\text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = n^1 = n. \quad (8.0.9)$$

If n is not a prime:

$$n^{\text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]}} = n^0 = 1. \quad (8.0.10)$$

To construct the factorial of the prime numbers up to n , we simply need to define the product of the numbers from 3 to n with the algebraic check *IsPrime* raised to the power of each multiplier n .

$$P_n! = 2 \prod_{i=3}^n n^{\prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} B_{\binom{n}{k}}^{[0\vee 1]}} = 2 \prod_{i=3}^n n^{\prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} (\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor)}. \quad (8.0.11)$$

We place 2 as a separate multiplier in front of the product, as 2 does not participate in the check, but it is still a prime number.

This algorithm goes through all the numbers up to the given n and transforms those that are not prime to 1, while leaving the prime numbers as they are. Here is how the algorithm for $n = 8$ looks:

$$P_8! = 2.3^1.4^0.5^1.6^0.7^1.8^0 = 2.3.1.5.1.7.1 = 210. \quad (8.0.12)$$

$P_8!$ represents the product of the first 4 prime numbers — 2, 3, 5, and 7. However, we do not know how many prime numbers there are up to a given n . This is also the main question in number theory. In a moment, we will construct an algorithm to find the factorial of the first n prime numbers.

Before doing that, let's define the factorial of composite numbers up to n . All we need to do is change the logic of the *IsPrime* check so that it returns the opposite result.

$$IsComposite_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} B_{\left(\frac{n}{k}\right)}^{[0\vee 1]}. \quad (8.0.13)$$

Thus, for $n = 10$:

$$IsComposite_{(10)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1 - (\lceil \frac{10}{2} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{10}{2} \rfloor)(\lceil \frac{10}{3} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{10}{3} \rfloor)(\lceil \frac{10}{4} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{10}{4} \rfloor) = 1 - 0.1.1 = 1. \quad (8.0.14)$$

The factorial of composite numbers will be denoted by $C_n!$.

$$C_n! = \prod_{i=3}^n n^{(1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} (\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor))}. \quad (8.0.15)$$

For $n = 8$:

$$C_8! = 3^0.4^1.5^0.6^1.7^0.8^1 = 4.6.8 = 192. \quad (8.0.16)$$

$C_n!$ can also be represented as the quotient:

$$C_n! = \frac{n!}{P_n!}. \quad (8.0.17)$$

For $n!$ we have:

$$n! = P_n!C_n!. \quad (8.0.18)$$

Let's verify this for $n = 8$:

$$8! = 2.(3.1).(1.4).(5.1).(1.6).(7.1).(1.8) = 210.192 = 40320. \quad (8.0.19)$$

In the above product of the algorithms, the first factor in the parentheses comes from $P_n!$, and the second from $C_n!$.

To find the factorial of the first n prime numbers, we first need to be able to count them. We can easily do this by once again using the algebraic check *IsPrime*. We will define a

sum of such checks for each natural number up to a given n . We will denote this sum by $\#P(n)$, instead of the well-known notation from number theory $\pi(n)$, since the latter represents a completely different type of operation.

$$\#P(n) = 1 + \sum_{i=3}^n \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} B_{\binom{n}{k}}^{[0\vee 1]}, \quad (8.0.20)$$

$$\#P(n) = 1 + \sum_{i=3}^n \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} (\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor). \quad (8.0.21)$$

We add one to the sum again because the number 2 does not participate in the check.

Let's see how the sum for $n = 11$ looks.

$$\#P(11) = 1 + 1 + 0 + 1 + 0 + 1 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 1 = 5. \quad (8.0.22)$$

Similarly, the number of composite numbers up to n can be found using the check *IsComposite*.

$$\#C(n) = \sum_{i=4}^n (1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} B_{\binom{n}{k}}^{[0\vee 1]}), \quad (8.0.23)$$

$$\#C(n) = \sum_{i=4}^n (1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} (\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor)). \quad (8.0.24)$$

We check for $n = 11$.

$$\#C(11) = 1 + 0 + 1 + 0 + 1 + 1 + 1 + 0 = 5. \quad (8.0.25)$$

Now we can proceed to deriving a formula for the factorial of the first N prime numbers. To do this, we will define another algebraic check, whose function will be to determine whether the current iteration has reached the n -th prime number. We will call this check *PCount* and it has the following form:

$$\text{PCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lceil \frac{1 + \frac{N - \#P(n)}{|E_{(N - \#P(n))}|}}{2} \rceil, \quad (8.0.26)$$

$$\text{PCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad N \geq \#P(n), \quad (8.0.27)$$

$$\text{PCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad N < \#P(n). \quad (8.0.28)$$

In other words, *PCount* checks whether the number of prime numbers up to a given natural number n is greater or equal than N . This check is of the type of checks *Greater* and

Less, which we defined at the beginning of the main discussion, but it is slightly different. Let's recall *Greater*.

$$\text{Greater}_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = \lfloor \frac{1 + \frac{x-l}{|E_{\lceil \frac{1}{1\vee x-l} \rceil}|}}{2} \rfloor, \quad (1.3.49)$$

$$Greater_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad x > l, \quad (8.0.29)$$

$$Greater_{(x,l)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad x \leq l. \quad (8.0.30)$$

While *Greater* asks the question, "Is x greater than l ?" and responds with 1 if it is indeed greater, *PCount* asks, "Is N greater than or equal to $\#P(n)$?" The difference comes from the ceiling and floor functions in the two checks.

We will add *PCount* check as a factor in the exponent of the formula for $P_n!$, but before that, we need to adjust the upper limit of the product in it. We will make the product infinite by setting the upper limit to the symbol ∞ because we do not know when the iterations will reach the n -th prime number.

For the factorial of the first n prime numbers, we will use the notation $N_p!$. Then:

$$N_p! = 2 \prod_{n=3}^{\infty} n^{\text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{PCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]}}. \quad (8.0.31)$$

In a more complete algebraic form:

$$N_p! = 2 \prod_{n=3}^{\infty} n^{\prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} (\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor) \lceil \frac{1 + \frac{N - \#P(n)}{|E(N - \#P(n))|}}{2} \rceil}}. \quad (8.0.32)$$

Let's see how the formula works. Let's find the 4th prime factorial.

$$4_p! = 2.3^{(1.1)} 4^{(0.1)} 5^{(1.1)} 6^{(0.1)} 7^{(1.1)} 8^{(0.0)} 9^{(0.0)} 10^{(0.0)} 11^{(1.0)} .1.1... \quad (8.0.33)$$

$$4_p! = 2.3.1.5.1.7.1.1.1.1...1 = 210 \quad (8.0.34)$$

On the fifth prime number 11 *PCount* changes the coefficient from 1 to 0, which automatically turns all subsequent factors n into ones. In this way, the infinite product accounts only for the natural factors that are prime numbers up to the desired count of prime numbers.

Similarly, the formula for the factorial of the first N composite numbers is:

$$N_c! = \prod_{n=4}^{\infty} n^{\text{IsComposite}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{CCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]}}. \quad (8.0.35)$$

where

$$\text{CCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 1, \quad N \geq \#C(n), \quad (8.0.36)$$

$$\text{CCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]} = 0, \quad N < \#C(n). \quad (8.0.37)$$

In a more complete algebraic form:

$$N_c! = \prod_{n=4}^{\infty} n^{\left(1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor\right) \lceil \frac{1 + \frac{N - \#C(n)}{|E(N - \#C(n))|}}{2} \rceil}}. \quad (8.0.38)$$

Lts's check for $N = 4$:

$$4_c! = 4^{(1.1)}5^{(0.1)}6^{(1.1)}7^{(0.1)}8^{(1.1)}9^{(1.1)}10^{(1.0)}11^{(0.0)}\dots 1 = 4.1.6.1.8.9.1\dots 1 = 1728. \quad (8.0.39)$$

After the factorials, we will now define the sums of prime and composite numbers.

Similarly, for the sums, we will make similar distinctions and divide them into the sum of prime numbers up to n and the sum of the first N prime numbers.

We begin with the sum of prime numbers up to n , which we will denote as $S_{P(n)}$. We will build upon the fundamental factorial expression, which took a given number n and returned the number itself if it is prime, or 1 if it's not. However, to construct a sum, we need to modify this so that it returns 0 if the number is not prime and the number itself if it is prime. We can achieve this easily by using the check *IsPrime* once again, but this time as a multiplier in front of n . Then we have:

$$S_{P(n)} = 2 + \sum_{i=3}^n \text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} n^{\text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]}}, \quad (8.0.40)$$

$$S_{P(n)} = 2 + \sum_{i=3}^n \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left(\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor \right) n^{\prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left(\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor \right)}. \quad (8.0.41)$$

We check for $n = 8$:

$$S_{P(8)} = 2 + 1.3^1 + 0.4^0 + 1.5^1 + 0.6^0 + 1.7^1 + 0.8^0 = 2 + 3 + 5 + 7 = 17. \quad (8.0.42)$$

Sum of composite numbers up to n :

$$S_{C(n)} = \sum_{i=4}^n \text{IsComposite}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} n^{\text{IsComposite}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]}} \quad (8.0.43)$$

$$S_{C(n)} = \sum_{i=4}^n \left(1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left(\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor \right) \right) n^{\left(1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left(\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor \right) \right)}. \quad (8.0.44)$$

Check for $n = 10$:

$$S_{C(10)} = 1.4^1 + 0.5^0 + 1.6^1 + 0.7^0 + 1.8^1 + 1.9^1 + 1.10^1 = 4 + 6 + 8 + 9 + 10 = 37. \quad (8.0.45)$$

Now we will derive formulas for the sum of the first N prime and the first N composite numbers. For the correct resetting of the current number, we will add *PCount* as a multiplier in front of n .

$$S_{N_p} = 2 + \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{PCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]} n^{\text{IsPrime}_{(n)}^{[0\vee 1]} \text{PCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0\vee 1]}}, \quad (8.0.46)$$

$$S_{N_p} = 2 + \sum_{n=3}^{\infty} \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left(\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor \right) \lceil \frac{1 + \frac{N - \#P(n)}{|E_{(N - \#P(n))}|}}{2} \rceil n^{\prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left(\lceil \frac{n}{k} \rceil - \lfloor \frac{n}{k} \rfloor \right) \lceil \frac{1 + \frac{N - \#P(n)}{|E_{(N - \#P(n))}|}}{2} \rceil}. \quad (8.0.47)$$

Let's check for $N = 3$.

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{3_p} &= 2 + (1.1) \cdot 3^{1.1} + (0.1) \cdot 4^{0.1} + (1.1) \cdot 5^{1.1} + (0.1) \cdot 6^{0.1} \\
&\quad + (1.0) \cdot 7^{1.0} + (0.0) \cdot 8^{0.0} + (0.0) \cdot 9^{0.0} + \dots \\
&= 2 + 3 + 0 + 5 + 0 + 0 + 0 + 0 + \dots + 0 = 10.
\end{aligned}$$

Although 7 is a prime number, it is the 4-th prime number, but $PCount$ returns 0 for $N > 3$, and therefore 7 is set to 0.

The formula for the first N composite numbers is analogous:

$$S_{N_c} = \sum_{n=4}^{\infty} \text{IsComposite}_{(n)}^{[0 \vee 1]} \text{CCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0 \vee 1]} n^{\text{IsComposite}_{(n)}^{[0 \vee 1]} \text{CCount}_{(N,n)}^{[0 \vee 1]}}, \quad (8.0.48)$$

$$S_{N_c} = \sum_{n=4}^{\infty} \left(1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left[\frac{n}{k} \right] - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{k} \right\rfloor \right) \left[\frac{1 + \frac{N - \#C(n)}{|E_{(N - \#C(n))}|}}{2} \right] n^{(1 - \prod_{k=2}^{\lceil \sqrt{n} \rceil} \left[\frac{n}{k} \right] - \left\lfloor \frac{n}{k} \right\rfloor) \left[\frac{1 + \frac{N - \#C(n)}{|E_{(N - \#C(n))}|}}{2} \right]}. \quad (8.0.49)$$

Sum of the first 3 composite numbers:

$$\begin{aligned}
S_{3_c} &= (1.1) \cdot 4^{1.1} + (0.1) \cdot 5^{0.1} + (1.1) \cdot 6^{1.1} + (0.1) \cdot 7^{0.1} \\
&\quad + (1.1) \cdot 8^{1.1} + (1.0) \cdot 9^{1.0} + \dots \\
&= 4 + 0 + 6 + 0 + 8 + 0 + \dots + 0 = 18.
\end{aligned}$$

With this formula, the discussion in this section comes to an end. In conclusion, we can say that adopting the expression $0^0 = 1$ provides a purely algebraic approach to performing operations commonly found in programming. The algebraic checks based on this assumption are the mathematical analog of *if-else* checks in programming languages. They enable the mathematical representation of complex algorithms, just as it is done in programming, as long as one works with numbers. The assumption $0^0 = 1$ also allows for the definition of mathematical analogs of certain data structures in programming - such as arrays and dictionaries. As we have seen above, it also enables control over the output of a given function by directly influencing the input parameter without modifying the function itself.